

Conformity of Classroom Observation with Teaching Practices

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ABSTRACT

The study explored how classroom observations truly reflect what teachers do in their daily teaching. It also examined the challenges teachers face during observation, how they cope with them, and the alignment of observed practices with actual teaching. Using a descriptive-correlational design and qualitative methods, data were gathered from selected elementary school teachers in Puerto Princesa City, District II through a structured survey questionnaire and follow-up interviews. Results showed that most respondents were classroom teachers with less than fifteen years of experience, mainly handling intermediate grades and core subjects like Mathematics, English, and Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao. Teachers consistently

showed effective teaching practices, especially in classroom management, use of instructional materials, and teaching strategies. The qualitative findings revealed that teachers experienced initial nervousness and anxiety during observations but employed coping strategies such as smiling, deep breathing, adjusting their mindset, and focusing on student engagement to regain confidence. Challenges included time pressure, lesson adjustments, and performance anxiety, which were addressed through early preparation, classroom organization, and support from colleagues. The findings revealed no significant relationship between teachers' practices, challenges, and coping mechanisms, implying that these factors are shaped more by individual disposition and context than by teaching skills alone. The study concludes that classroom observations generally mirror teachers' real practices, but pressures during observation can still affect performance. It recommends creating a more supportive observation culture—one that values fairness, constructive feedback, and professional growth.

Keywords: *classroom observation, teaching practices, challenges, coping mechanisms, professional growth, qualitative insights, quality education*

INTRODUCTION

Classroom observations were widely used in schools as a tool to evaluate teaching performance, improve instructional practices, and guide professional development. These observations were often structured and graded, using standardized tools to assess specific teaching behaviors. However, the integrity of such evaluations had been critically examined. Kim and Kim (2020) emphasized that the pressure to perform during observations often compelled teachers to alter their usual classroom routines to meet evaluation expectations. This behavior, while understandable, raised concerns about whether observations truly reflected authentic teaching. Labad et al. (2024) likewise noted that teachers tended to modify their practices during observations, aligning their actions with perceived standards rather than regular practice.

Kaymakamoglu (2018) also observed that contextual factors, such as large class sizes, limited instructional time, and policy demands, hindered teachers from consistently applying their philosophical approaches to teaching, further highlighting a divide between belief and practice. These findings suggested that classroom observation tools needed to be responsive to real classroom conditions to be effective and meaningful.

In the Philippine context, the Department of Education institutionalized the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) through DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2015. This policy aimed to enhance teacher evaluation by aligning performance assessments with the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST). One of the key components of RPMS was classroom observation, which served as both a formative and summative assessment tool. Gacutan (2020) emphasized that classroom observations should go beyond mere compliance and serve as authentic platforms for capturing instructional reality. However, concerns persisted regarding the validity of observation data. Barrogo (n.d.) argued that rigid rubrics could stifle teacher autonomy and creativity, making it difficult for educators to demonstrate their unique instructional styles. Likewise, Generalao et al. (2022) questioned whether current tools adequately captured the nuances of day-to-day teaching, especially given the standardized, checklist-driven format of most observation instruments.

Fayo and Hilario (2023) observed that classroom observations often captured a polished, rehearsed version of teaching rather than what truly happened in day-to-day instruction. In many cases, teachers designed lessons that aligned neatly with observation rubrics, not necessarily because these reflected their usual practice, but because they felt compelled to meet specific expectations. This tendency created a noticeable gap between what was observed and what took place in classrooms. Guliman and Gerodias (2024) warned that this mismatch could undermine the credibility and reliability of classroom evaluations. Recognizing this, Salpocial and Palma (2023) emphasized the importance of grounding observation systems in authentic teaching—those everyday moments that reflected real student needs and instructional decisions. They argued that doing so not only provided more accurate evaluations but also better supported teacher development and student learning. Echoing this, Marzano (2024) stressed that meaningful observations should happen within a culture of trust—one that encouraged professional dialogue, self-reflection, and constructive feedback tailored to the teacher's context.

The COVID-19 pandemic introduced new dynamics to classroom observations. Angeles, Naparan, Celesio, and Ecot (2023) reported that even amid remote teaching, teachers continued to engage in observations, often through Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions. These required teachers to plan strategically, adopt health protocols, and integrate new technologies. Challenges such as unreliable internet connectivity, unfamiliarity with digital tools, and peer pressure underscored the need for better ICT training, infrastructure support, and clearer orientation on RPMS-PPST indicators. Similarly, Milenković (2024) stressed the importance of systemic support in observation protocols to ensure equity and effectiveness in both traditional and online contexts. Perception played a pivotal role in how teachers received and responded to classroom observations. Torres, Zerrudo, Labad, and Gabales (2024) emphasized that when observations were conducted with professionalism, transparency, and mutual respect, they were more likely to be perceived as tools for development rather than surveillance. Thom (2020) argued that teachers' willingness to improve hinged largely on whether they viewed the feedback process as credible and empowering. However, when observers lacked consistency or failed to provide actionable feedback, the process became less meaningful. Archer et al. (2016) and Reños and Pontillas (2024) similarly highlighted that trust, fairness, and follow-up support were essential to building positive perceptions of observation practices. While classroom observations were designed to assess teaching effectiveness, a significant gap remained in understanding how these evaluations aligned with actual daily teaching. Most existing systems focused on performance during scheduled, high-stakes observations, which might not have reflected the real complexities and nuances of everyday instruction. Teachers often prepared lessons specifically to satisfy observation criteria, leading to a performance that differed from their usual classroom strategies. This disconnects raised concerns about the credibility of the observation process and its usefulness in

guiding authentic professional growth. Despite a wealth of research highlighting the potential benefits and pitfalls of classroom observation, limited studies focused on how teachers and master teachers perceived the alignment between observation and actual practice within the framework of RPMS and PPST. Addressing this gap could lead to the development of more responsive and meaningful observation systems that reflected the realities of teaching and supported educators more effectively.

Therefore, the study aimed to determine the challenges encountered by teachers during the conduct of classroom observation and the coping mechanisms they employed to address these challenges. Reños and Pontillas (2024) found that public school teachers in the Philippines cited a lack of preparation time, peer pressure, and misalignment between the observation rubric and real classroom conditions as significant stressors. Bhebhe and Nxumalo (2015) reported that in Zimbabwean secondary schools, teachers experienced heightened performance anxiety due to the pressure of being evaluated, often perceiving observations as punitive rather than supportive. Chiou (2023), in a study on Taiwanese secondary school teachers, found that structured lesson preparation, emotional regulation, and mindfulness strategies were key methods for coping with observation-related stress. Similarly, Marzaini, Yusof, and Halim (2024) discovered that Malaysian teachers often relied on peer collaboration, faith-based practices like prayer, and repetition of lessons as coping mechanisms.

This study examined the conformity of classroom observation with actual teaching practices among selected elementary schools in the Division of Puerto Princesa City, District II. It described the demographic and school profiles of respondents and identified common teaching practices in terms of strategies, materials, classroom management, time management, and assessment. The study also determined the challenges encountered during classroom observation and the coping mechanisms employed by teachers. Furthermore, it analyzed the relationships between teaching practices, challenges, and coping mechanisms to assess how classroom observations reflect real and routine teaching practices.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. *Conceptual Framework*

The conceptual framework of this study examined how various factors influenced the perceptions of teachers and master teachers in the Division of Puerto Princesa City, District II, regarding classroom observation and the extent to which these perceptions aligned with their actual teaching practices. The independent variables include the respondents' demographic characteristics such as their position or rank, years of teaching experience, grade level handled or subject taught, and educational attainment. School-related factors such as school size classification, number of teaching staff, and availability of instructional facilities and materials were also considered. These personal and institutional factors provided the background context that may have shaped how teachers and master teachers viewed and experienced classroom observations. The framework would also identify the challenges encountered by the teachers' respondents during classroom observation and the coping mechanisms teachers employed to address the challenges they encountered during the conduct of classroom observation as a moderating variable. The dependent variable would be the teachers' and master teachers' conformity to classroom observations and teaching practices.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a mixed-methods design combining quantitative-descriptive and qualitative-exploratory approaches. The quantitative component gathered structured data on teachers' profiles, classroom practices, and challenges using a survey questionnaire, while the qualitative component explored in-depth experiences and coping mechanisms through descriptive responses. This approach enabled a comprehensive understanding of teachers' practices and the realities of classroom observation.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in fifteen (15) purposively selected elementary schools in the Division of Puerto Princesa City, District II, categorized into big, medium, and small schools to ensure balanced representation. Big schools included Mateo Jagmis Memorial ES, Sta. Monica ES, Loreto Santos Lanzanas Memorial ES, Sicsican ES, and Tiniguiban ES; medium schools included Mangingisda ES, Matahimik Bucana ES, Sta. Lourdes ES, Tagbuross ES, and Abanico ES; while small schools included Bualbualan ES, Iratag ES, Napsan ES, Simpokan ES, and Kandes ES. This classification allowed for comparison across varying school contexts.

Respondents

The respondents of the study consisted of teachers and master teachers from selected elementary schools in the Division of Puerto Princesa City, District II, who were directly involved in classroom observation. Master Teachers conducted observations of classroom teachers, while Head Teachers and School Principals also observed Master Teachers, ensuring representation across different levels of instructional supervision.

Population and Sample

The computed sample size was derived from the total population of teachers and master teachers in the Division of Puerto Princesa City, District II. Applying Cochran's formula, a representative sample size of two hundred twenty (220) respondents was determined. To ensure fair representation, the sample was distributed proportionally across the twenty-eight (28) participating schools based on each school's percentage share of the total population.

Research Instrument

A researcher-made survey questionnaire was used to assess teachers' and master teachers' perceptions of classroom observation and its alignment with actual teaching practices. The instrument consisted of five parts: Part I covered respondents' demographic profile; Part II described the school profile; Part III assessed common teaching practices in terms of strategies, instructional materials, classroom management, time management, and assessment; Part IV identified challenges encountered during classroom observation; and Part V explored coping mechanisms employed by teachers to address these challenges.

Data Collection and Analysis

Prior to data collection, permission was secured from the Schools Division Office of Puerto Princesa City and school administrators, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents. Questionnaires were distributed in printed form through school focal persons, ensuring accessibility and confidentiality. Quantitative data from Parts I–III were analyzed using mean and standard deviation, while responses on challenges and coping mechanisms (Parts IV–V) were categorized and ranked. Qualitative data from follow-up interviews were analyzed thematically to provide deeper insights. This combined approach ensured a comprehensive understanding of teachers' practices, challenges, and perceptions of classroom observation.

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to ethical standards by ensuring voluntary participation, informed consent, and the right of respondents to withdraw at any time without penalty. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained, and all data were used solely for academic purposes. Proper citation of sources was observed to uphold academic integrity and avoid plagiarism.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Profile of the Teachers' Respondents

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the respondents, providing a clear picture of the teachers who participated in the study. The data show that 175 teachers, comprising 80%, are classroom teachers, while 45 teachers, comprising 20%, are master teachers. This indicates that the participants represent both those who regularly undergo classroom observations and those who may serve as observers or mentors, allowing for a more balanced understanding of the topic. This composition reflects the instructional-centered nature of basic education institutions, where classroom teaching remains the core responsibility of educators (Bernardo, 2019). According to De la Cruz and Roldan (2021), the limited number of higher-ranking teachers is often due to higher qualification requirements and the competitive nature of promotion systems in the Department of Education. Similarly, Ramos (2020) emphasized that the majority of teachers remain at the Teacher I to Teacher III levels for several years, largely due to limited promotion slots and the need for advanced academic credentials or specialized training. This workforce structure, while ensuring a strong teaching presence, may also indicate the need for more professional advancement opportunities and mentoring support. As Sison and Hernandez (2023) noted, when most teachers remain in teaching-focused positions, continuous professional development and recognition systems become essential to sustain motivation, enhance instructional quality, and prepare more teachers for leadership roles within the education system.

In terms of teaching experience, 111 teachers or 50% have been in service for 6 to 15 years, 81 teachers or 37% for 1 to 5 years, and 28 teachers or 13% for 16 to 27 years. This distribution reflects a diverse range of teaching experiences, combining perspectives from both relatively new and more seasoned

educators. Such variation helps present a broader view of how teachers at different career stages approach and respond to classroom observations.

Several studies have noted that educators with less than 15 years of experience typically belong to the early- and mid-career stages, where professional identity and pedagogical mastery are still being refined through continuous practice and mentorship (Flores & Day, 2020). According to Torres and Mendoza (2021), early-career teachers often focus on mastering classroom management and instructional delivery, while mid-career teachers begin to integrate more reflective and learner-centered approaches. Similarly, Dela Peña and Santos (2022) emphasized that teachers within their first decade of service tend to experience significant professional growth when provided with supportive feedback and opportunities for development. These findings suggest that the predominance of early- to mid-career educators highlights the importance of sustained capacity-building programs to help teachers further consolidate their competencies and achieve long-term professional stability and excellence.

Regarding grade levels handled, 63 teachers or 29% teach Grade 5, 41 teachers or 19% teach Grade 6, 35 teachers or 16% teach Grade 2, 30 teachers or 14% teach Grade 1, 29 teachers or 13% teach Grade 4, and 22 teachers or 10% teach Grade 3. This indicates that a significant number of respondents are handling upper-grade learners, where lessons often require deeper content mastery and greater classroom management skills.

The distribution of teachers across different grade levels and subject areas reflects the multifaceted role of educators in ensuring comprehensive learning in basic education. Studies have shown that in many Philippine public schools, a higher concentration of teachers is assigned to intermediate grades where foundational and higher-order thinking skills are developed (Cruz & Javier, 2021). Handling multiple subjects is also common, particularly in elementary education, where teachers are expected to demonstrate versatility and adapt to varying content areas (Castro & Ramirez, 2020). This practice promotes instructional continuity and fosters stronger teacher-student relationships, though it can also pose challenges in workload balance and subject specialization (Domingo & Reyes, 2022).

For the subjects taught, 154 teachers or 70% teach ESP, 91 teachers or 41% teach Mathematics, 76 teachers or 35% teach AP, 72 teachers or 33% teach English, 71 teachers or 32% teach SCI, 48 teachers or 22% teach MAPEH, 42 teachers or 19% teach Filipino, and 9 teachers or 4% teach EPP. The representation of different subject areas highlights the varied instructional contexts in which teachers experience classroom observation.

Meanwhile, the prominence of core subjects such as Mathematics, English, and Araling Panlipunan highlights their centrality in the K-12 curriculum as vehicles for cognitive and civic development. Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao (EsP), on the other hand, serves as a moral compass for learners, instilling essential Filipino values and social responsibility (Santos & Rivera, 2023). Collectively, these findings underscore that teachers' flexibility across grade levels and disciplines remains vital to the holistic formation of learners in the basic education system.

In terms of educational attainment, 148 teachers or 67% hold a Bachelor's Degree, 58 teachers or 26% have earned units in a Master's program, and 14 teachers or 6% have completed a Master's Degree. These figures show a teaching workforce that continues to pursue professional growth through further studies, which may influence their perspectives and practices during observations.

In the Philippine context, most public-school teachers hold a bachelor's degree as the minimum qualification for entry into the teaching profession, in accordance with the Department of Education and the Professional Regulation Commission's requirements (Garcia & Santos, 2021). However, a growing number of teachers have begun to pursue graduate studies, reflecting their increasing commitment to lifelong learning and professional advancement (Delos Reyes, 2022). Studies by Navarro and Cruz (2020) reveal that teachers who engage in postgraduate education tend to demonstrate stronger pedagogical skills, improved research literacy, and a deeper understanding of learner diversity. Similarly, Manalo and De Guzman (2023) emphasized that advanced academic preparation enhances teachers' confidence and opens

more opportunities for promotion and leadership roles. This trend suggests that the pursuit of higher education among teachers not only enriches their professional competence but also contributes to the overall improvement of the quality of education in schools.

The data implies that, the demographic profile in Table 3 reflects a diverse group of educators in terms of position, experience, grade level, subject area, and academic qualification. This diversity strengthens the study by offering insights from different teaching contexts and professional backgrounds, enriching the understanding of teachers' experiences during classroom observation.

Table 3. The Demographic profile of the respondents

	n=Frequency	Percentage
Position		
Teacher	175	80%
Master Teacher	45	20%
Years in Teaching		
1 to 5 years	81	37%
6 to 15 years	111	50%
16 to 27 years	28	13%
Grade Level Handled		
Grade 1	30	14%
Grade 2	35	16%
Grade 3	22	10%
Grade 4	29	13%
Grade 5	63	29%
Grade 6	41	19%
Subjects Taught		
English	72	33%
Filipino	42	19%
Mathematics	91	41%
Science	71	32%
Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao	154	70%
MAPEH	48	22%
Araling Panlipunan	76	35%
Edukasyong Pantahanan at Pangkabuhayan	9	4%
Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	148	67%
With Units for Master's	58	26%
Master's Degree	14	6%

**Multiple Response Allowed*

Respondents' School Profile

Table 4 presents the school profile of the respondents, providing insight into the learning environments where teachers perform their instructional duties and undergo classroom observations. The data indicate that 145 schools or 66% are large school, 59 schools or 27% are medium-sized school, and 16 schools or 7% are small school. This distribution implies that a greater portion of teachers work in institutions with larger populations, where observation systems and administrative supervision are more formalized. In contrast, teachers in smaller schools may experience more personalized interactions but with fewer available resources. According to Villanueva and Ramos (2022), larger schools tend to have higher student populations, which require greater teacher deployment and organizational efficiency to maintain effective learning environments. However, this expansion often results in limited instructional supervision due to the small number of master teachers relative to the total teaching staff (Cabrera & Dizon, 2021).

For the teachers-to-master-teacher ratio, the most common ratio is 10:1 with 73 schools or 33%, followed by 5:1 with 49 schools or 22%, 14:1 with 42 schools or 19%, 7:1 with 18 schools or 8%, 22:1 with 18 schools or 8%, 15:1 with 15 schools or 3%, 3:1 with 1 school or 1%, and no master teacher in 7 schools or 5%. These figures suggest that while some schools maintain manageable mentoring ratios, others have a higher number of teachers per master teacher, potentially affecting the frequency and quality of feedback during classroom observations. This imbalance restricts opportunities for mentoring and professional coaching, key elements in sustaining teacher growth and improving classroom instruction. Similarly, Fernandez and De Castro (2023) emphasized that the presence of experienced master teachers significantly contributes to a culture of instructional excellence, yet many schools still face shortages in such positions, particularly in public elementary settings.

In terms of instructional facilities and materials, all schools have functional classrooms or 100% and LCD projectors and televisions or 100%, indicating that teachers have access to basic tools necessary for lesson delivery and demonstration. Internet access is available in 211 schools or 96%, learning modules or textbooks in 210 schools or 95%, and libraries in 206 schools or 94%, reflecting schools' readiness to support teaching and learning activities. However, audio-visual equipment is present in only 41 schools or 19%, and none of the schools reported having laboratory rooms or 0%, suggesting that practical or experimental lessons may be less emphasized in these learning settings.

Studies by Mendoza (2020) and Aquino et al. (2023) highlighted that while most Philippine public schools possess basic facilities such as classrooms, libraries, and learning modules, access to advanced resources like laboratories, audio-visual tools, and modern technologies remains limited. This uneven distribution of facilities contributes to disparities in instructional quality, particularly in schools located outside urban centers. Moreover, Espinosa and Bartolome (2021) stressed that adequate access to ICT and multimedia tools enhances lesson delivery, supports differentiated instruction, and encourages active learning. Hence, ensuring equitable distribution of teaching resources and strengthening mentorship structures are essential to improving educational outcomes across schools of varying sizes and capacities.

The data reflect that the school environments are generally conducive to teaching and classroom observation but with certain resource gaps that could limit instructional innovation. This implies that teachers appear to benefit from access to digital tools and structured classrooms, yet the lack of specialized facilities such as laboratories points to areas where support for hands-on or experiential learning could still be strengthened.

Table 4. School profile of respondents

	Frequency	Percentage
School Size		
Small	16	7%
Medium	59	27%
Large	145	66%
Teachers-to-Masters Ratio		
No Master Teacher	7	5%
3:1	1	1%
5:1	49	22%
7:1	18	8%
10:1	73	33%
14:1	42	19%
15:1	15	3%
22:1	18	8%
Availability of Instructional Facilities and Materials*		
Functional Classrooms	220	100%
Library	206	94%
Internet Access	211	96%

Audio-Visual Equipment	41	19%
Laboratory Rooms	0	0%
Learning Modules/Textbooks	210	95%
LCD projector/ TV	220	100%

**Multiple Response Allowed*

The Common Teaching Practices of the Teachers' Respondents

Table 5 presents the common teaching practices of the teachers' respondents in terms of: (1) teaching strategies, (2) instructional materials, (3) classroom management, (4) time management, and (5) assessment and evaluation. Data reveals an overall mean score of 4.52 indicates that teachers *always* exhibit best teaching practices in their daily instruction.

Among the five domains, classroom management recorded the highest mean with 4.98, *always*, suggesting that teachers consistently maintain a well-managed, positive, and conducive learning environment. This highlights their strong ability to establish order, enforce rules, and sustain learner engagement during lessons.

Teaching strategies obtained a mean rating of 4.59, *always*, indicating that teachers consistently employ a variety of methods to accommodate the different learning styles of their students. It reflects teachers' strong commitment to ensuring that lessons are engaging, inclusive, and responsive to learners' needs. They often adjust their teaching methods based on students' progress and encourage active participation in class, demonstrating their focus on learner-centered instruction.

This shows that they consistently employ a wide range of strategies to address the diverse learning styles of their pupils. The highest-rated statements include the use of various teaching strategies with a mean of 4.95, *always*, and the encouragement of active student participation which also has a mean of 4.95, *always*. These findings reveal that teachers are highly adaptive in their methods and value the active involvement of students in learning. They also adjust their teaching based on students' needs and progress with a mean of 4.91, *always*, which highlights their responsiveness to learner differences. On the other hand, integrating real-world applications and using a variety of teaching approaches are both rated with means of 4.06 and 4.07, *often*. This suggests that while teachers are aware of the importance of connecting lessons to real-life situations, such practices may not always be fully implemented due to time or curricular constraints.

Instructional materials received a mean rating of 4.58, *always*, signifying that teachers consistently prepare and utilize appropriate learning resources to support effective classroom instruction. The use of a wide range of instructional materials obtained a mean of 4.04, *often*, indicating that teachers frequently incorporate different teaching aids such as charts, visual tools, and printed resources to address various learning preferences. Creating or adapting instructional materials received a mean of 4.05, *often*, which suggests that teachers take the initiative to design or modify their own resources, when necessary, although limitations in time and resources may occasionally affect this process. The incorporation of multimedia resources like videos, slides, and online content was rated 4.94, *always*, reflecting the teachers' consistent use of technology to make learning more interactive and engaging. This practice highlights the teachers' efforts to align with 21st-century teaching standards that emphasize digital literacy and technological integration in instruction. Ensuring that instructional materials are clear, organized, and easy to understand obtained a mean of 4.95, *always*, the highest among the subthemes, demonstrating that teachers value clarity and structure in their materials to facilitate better comprehension among students. Regularly evaluating and updating teaching materials earned a mean of 4.94, *always*, showing that teachers are committed to maintaining the relevance and accuracy of their instructional content. This indicates a continuous effort to improve learning resources in line with curriculum updates and students' changing needs.

These results reveal that teachers primarily used instructional materials and tools with which they felt most comfortable. This familiarity allowed them to manage lessons confidently, adapt to classroom

needs, and maintain student engagement, demonstrating a practical approach to instructional delivery based on their comfort and experience.

Classroom management achieved the highest overall mean of 4.98, *always*. This demonstrates their strong ability to maintain order, discipline, and a positive learning environment. Teachers reported always addressing disruptive behavior calmly and constructively with a perfect mean of 5.00, *always*, which shows their professionalism and composure in handling challenges. They also consistently use positive reinforcement with a mean of 4.99, *always* and maintain a respectful classroom atmosphere with a mean of 4.98, *always*. These findings reflect a nurturing environment where students feel respected and motivated to learn. The establishment and enforcement of classroom rules with means of 4.94 and 4.98, *always*, respectively indicate that teachers provide clear expectations and ensure consistent implementation to promote discipline and harmony in the classroom.

Time management has a mean of 4.04, *often*, suggesting that teachers generally manage their time well, although occasional challenges in pacing lessons and minimizing non-instructional activities may arise due to class size, varied learner needs, or limited instructional periods.

Teachers use time efficiently to meet lesson objectives with a mean of 4.09, *often* and manage transitions smoothly between activities with a mean of 4.04, *often*. These results indicate that most teachers are able to maintain lesson flow and avoid unnecessary interruptions. However, allocating sufficient time for lesson parts, adjusting lesson pacing, and minimizing non-instructional activities received slightly lower means of 4.03, 4.01, and 4.02, *often*, respectively. These findings imply that teachers sometimes face challenges related to time constraints, lesson pacing, and competing tasks, which may affect their ability to maximize instructional time.

Assessment and evaluation practices were rated 3.99 to 4.96, *often*, indicating that teachers regularly assess learners' understanding and provide constructive feedback, but they only often align assessments with learning objectives and encourage self-assessment, indicating an area for further enhancement.

The highest-rated item is the regular assessment of students' understanding with a mean of 4.96, *always*, followed by providing timely and constructive feedback with a mean of 4.95, *always*. These results emphasize that teachers are diligent in monitoring learners' progress and giving feedback that supports improvement. However, the use of varied assessment tools, encouragement of self-assessment, and alignment of assessments with learning objectives were rated with means of 4.05, 4.04, and 3.99, *often*, respectively. This suggests that while teachers practice assessment consistently, the diversity of evaluation methods and the integration of reflective assessment could be further enhanced.

Overall, the findings suggest that teachers demonstrate exemplary practices in classroom management and consistently apply diverse teaching strategies and instructional materials. Continuous improvement in time utilization and alignment of assessments with learning objectives could further strengthen the quality of teaching and learning experiences.

Numerous studies emphasize that teachers' consistent application of effective strategies—such as varied teaching methods, efficient classroom management, and appropriate use of instructional materials—directly contributes to student engagement and academic achievement (Marzano, 2024; Hattie, 2009). The findings of this study, which highlight teachers' strong performance in classroom management and instructional delivery, align with Marzano's (2024) assertion that organized, well-managed classrooms foster positive learning climates and higher student performance.

The effective use of instructional materials also enhances learners' understanding and motivation. According to Milenković (2024), instructional aids not only make learning more interactive but also help bridge the gap between abstract concepts and real-life application. Similarly, Bhebhe and Nxumalo (2015) found that the integration of relevant, context-based teaching resources significantly improves lesson retention and comprehension among learners. These findings resonate with the present study's observation that teachers actively utilize instructional materials to enrich their lessons.

Teaching strategies play a vital role in promoting differentiated learning and ensuring inclusivity. Archer et al. (2016) emphasized that effective educators employ a variety of teaching approaches tailored to learners' needs, thereby enhancing classroom participation and fostering deeper understanding. Likewise, Zaare (2012) noted that teachers who adapt strategies such as cooperative learning, inquiry-based instruction, and formative assessment demonstrate greater teaching efficacy and learner-centeredness. The respondents' consistent use of diverse teaching strategies suggests their adaptability and responsiveness to varied learner needs.

However, areas such as time management and assessment practices often present ongoing challenges. Myers (2012) observed that while teachers may excel in instructional delivery, managing instructional time efficiently remains a complex task, particularly when balancing administrative responsibilities and curriculum demands. Similarly, Reños and Pontillas (2024) emphasized the importance of aligning assessment tools with learning objectives to ensure meaningful evaluation of student performance. The slightly lower frequency of best practices in these areas, as shown in the results, suggests a need for continued training and support in maximizing instructional time and refining assessment design.

It supports the notion that consistent and reflective teaching practices form the backbone of instructional quality. As Granström et al. (2024) argued, teachers' professionalism and dedication are evident not only in their methods but also in their ongoing efforts to improve their craft. The respondents' strong adherence to effective classroom management, diverse strategies, and well-chosen materials thus exemplify the characteristics of competent, reflective educators committed to continuous improvement and learner success.

The findings imply that strong classroom management practices contribute significantly to maintaining a positive, orderly, and engaging learning environment. Sustaining this strength requires continuous support from school administrators through mentoring, monitoring, and collaborative professional activities to ensure consistency and long-term effectiveness.

The consistent use of varied teaching strategies suggests that teachers are responsive to learners' diverse needs. However, there is a need to further strengthen the integration of real-world applications in teaching to make learning more meaningful and relevant. Ongoing professional development can help teachers enhance innovative and learner-centered approaches.

The use of instructional materials indicates that teachers effectively utilize available resources, particularly multimedia tools. Expanding access to diverse and updated instructional materials, along with training in resource development, can further improve lesson delivery and student engagement also highlight a need to improve time management practices. Providing support through training on lesson pacing, efficient routines, and workload management can help teachers maximize instructional time and minimize disruptions. Assessment and evaluation practices require enhancement, particularly in aligning assessments with learning objectives and promoting self-assessment. Strengthening teachers' assessment literacy through targeted training can lead to more meaningful evaluation and improved student learning outcomes.

Overall, continuous professional development, adequate resource provision, and institutional support are essential in sustaining effective teaching practices and addressing identified areas for improvement.

Table 5. Common teaching practices of the teachers' respondents

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
A. TEACHING STRATEGIES		
1 I use a variety of teaching strategies to cater to different learning styles in my everyday teaching.	4.95	Always

2	I adjust my teaching methods based on students' needs and progress in my daily lessons.	4.91	Always
3	I encourage active student participation during lessons every day.	4.95	Always
4	I integrate real-world applications into my teaching strategies every day.	4.06	Often
5	I use a variety of teaching strategies to cater to different learning styles in my everyday teaching.	4.07	Often
Mean		4.59	Always
B. INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS			
1	I use a wide range of instructional materials to enhance student learning in my everyday teaching.	4.04	Often
2	I create or adapt instructional materials to better suit my students' needs in daily lessons.	4.05	Often
3	I incorporate multimedia resources (videos, slides, online content) into my everyday lessons.	4.94	Always
4	I ensure that instructional materials are clear, organized, and easy to understand in my daily teaching.	4.95	Always
5	I regularly evaluate and update my teaching materials to keep them relevant for everyday use.	4.94	Always
Mean		4.58	Always
C. CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT			
1	I establish clear rules and expectations at the start of each lesson during my everyday teaching.	4.94	Always
2	I daily maintain a positive and respectful classroom atmosphere.	4.98	Always
3	I consistently enforce classroom rules to ensure smooth operations in my everyday teaching.	4.98	Always
4	I address disruptive behavior calmly and constructively during my daily teaching.	5.00	Always
5	I regularly use positive reinforcement to motivate students in my everyday teaching.	4.99	Always
Mean		4.98	Always
D. TIME MANAGEMENT			
1	I allocate sufficient time for each section of my lesson plan during my everyday teaching.	4.03	Often
2	I adjust my lesson pacing based on students' understanding and engagement in daily lessons.	4.01	Often
3	I minimize time spent on non-instructional activities to focus on learning in my everyday teaching.	4.02	Often
4	I effectively manage transitions between lesson activities to avoid disruptions in my daily teaching.	4.04	Often
5	I use time efficiently to ensure all lesson objectives are met within the allocated period in daily lessons.	4.09	Often

Mean	4.04	Always
E. ASSESSMENT AND EVALUATION PRACTICES		
1 I regularly assess students' understanding during lessons in my everyday teaching.	4.96	Always
2 I use a variety of assessment tools (quizzes, projects, presentations) to evaluate student performance in daily lessons.	4.05	Often
3 I provide timely and constructive feedback to help students improve in my everyday teaching.	4.95	Always
4 I encourage students to self-assess their learning progress in my daily teaching.	4.04	Often
5 I align my assessments with the learning objectives of the lesson every day.	3.99	Often
Mean	4.40	Often
Overall Mean	4.52	Always

Legend:

1.0 – 1.49	<i>Never</i>
1.50 – 2.49	<i>Rarely</i>
2.50 – 3.49	<i>Sometimes</i>
3.50 – 4.49	<i>Often</i>
4.50 – 5.00	<i>Always</i>

Teaching Strategies

The results for teaching strategies indicate that teachers consistently employed a variety of instructional methods to address different learning styles, adjust to student needs, and encourage active participation. While core interactive strategies were used always, the integration of real-world applications and additional varied strategies occurred often, suggesting that teachers prioritized fundamental student-centered practices while occasionally incorporating contextual or innovative approaches. Overall, teaching strategies reflected a responsive and participatory approach in daily lessons.

Instructional Materials

In terms of instructional materials, teachers frequently ensured that materials were clear, organized, and up-to-date, and often incorporated multimedia resources to enhance learning. While adaptation and creation of materials to meet specific student needs occurred often, teachers tended to rely on tools they were most comfortable with. This approach allowed teachers to maintain lesson flow and student engagement while balancing creativity with familiarity.

Classroom Management

Classroom management received the highest ratings, indicating that teachers consistently maintained a positive and respectful learning environment, established clear rules, and enforced them constructively. They regularly used positive reinforcement and addressed disruptive behavior calmly, which supported smooth lesson delivery and promoted a motivating atmosphere for students. This demonstrates that teachers prioritized order, respect, and a student-centered environment in their everyday teaching.

Time Management

Time management practices were implemented often, with teachers allocating sufficient time for lesson sections, managing transitions, and adjusting pacing based on students' understanding. Although teachers made efforts to minimize non-instructional time and meet lesson objectives, full efficiency was

not consistently achieved, suggesting that time management remained a challenge in balancing lesson coverage and student engagement.

Assessment and Evaluation Practices

Assessment and evaluation practices showed that teachers regularly assessed student understanding and provided timely, constructive feedback. However, the use of varied assessment tools, encouraging self-assessment, and alignment with lesson objectives occurred often rather than always, indicating areas for improvement. Overall, assessment practices reflected a consistent focus on monitoring learning, supporting improvement, and guiding instructional decisions.

Challenges encountered by teachers' respondents during the conduct of classroom observation

Table 6 reveals the challenges encountered by the teachers' respondents during the conduct of classroom observation. The main challenge reported by most teachers was preparing instructional materials with limited time or resources; this concern was mentioned by 52% of the respondents, making it the top challenge (Rank 1). The second-ranked challenge (47%, Rank 2) involved adjusting or shortening lesson activities to meet time expectations. This shows a common struggle with pacing and delivering the curriculum during observations. The third-highest challenge (45%, Rank 3) dealt with instructional delivery and pressure. Teachers found it difficult to maintain fluency or confidence in their teaching methods under pressure. Challenges related to managing personal stress and emotional responses were both ranked the same (Rank 4.5). Maintaining composure and confidence during observations, as well as dealing with feelings of pressure or anticipation about feedback, were noted by 43% of the teachers.

These results suggest that the teachers' biggest anxieties come from logistical and preparation demands (Time/Resources and Lesson Pacing), which are ranked 1 and 2. While performance and emotional control are also important, the data shows that managing resources and time is crucial for easing the observational stress on teachers.

These findings emphasize that classroom observation, while a valuable tool for professional growth, can also be a source of stress that impacts teachers' natural teaching flow and comfort, suggesting the need for supportive observation practices and pre-observation preparation to reduce performance anxiety and logistical difficulties.

Several studies have shown that teachers often experience heightened anxiety and stress during observations, which can interfere with their natural teaching flow and authenticity. This phenomenon, commonly referred to as the Hawthorne Effect, suggests that individuals may alter their behavior when they are aware of being observed (Mayo, 1933; Sugot & Ladia, 2024). As a result, teachers might modify their instructional delivery or classroom interactions, not necessarily to improve learning outcomes but to meet perceived observer expectations.

Time constraints are among the most significant challenges teachers face during classroom observations. Myers (2012) noted that teachers frequently struggle to balance lesson pacing with limited instructional time, often condensing activities or skipping key learning components. Similarly, Chiou (2023) found that time pressure and administrative workload lead to compromised lesson planning and reduced instructional depth, particularly when teachers must prepare demonstration lessons specifically for evaluation. These findings echo the present study's results, highlighting the practical difficulty of aligning observation requirements with real classroom conditions.

The preparation of instructional materials is another major stressor for teachers. Marzaini et al. (2024) reported that the demand for visually appealing and well-structured lesson materials during observation periods can be time-consuming, often diverting attention from more meaningful instructional planning. Teachers tend to overprepare or modify their materials to meet observer expectations rather than focusing on learner-centered approaches. This aligns with the study's findings that the logistical load of preparing materials adds to the overall strain of the observation process.

Emotional and psychological pressures during classroom observation are well-documented in educational research. Bhebhe and Nxumalo (2015) emphasized that teachers often experience self-consciousness, fear of judgment, and anxiety over feedback, which can hinder their spontaneity and confidence in teaching. Granström et al. (2024) similarly found that teacher stress during observation can negatively affect classroom management and communication with students. When under observation, teachers often divide their attention between maintaining learner discipline and satisfying observer expectations, leading to decreased instructional fluidity and rapport with students.

The integration of technology and formal assessment procedures during observations adds another layer of difficulty. Thom (2020) noted that teachers frequently face challenges with unfamiliar tools and digital platforms, particularly when these are mandated for observation compliance rather than chosen for pedagogical fit. In the same vein, Archer et al. (2016) emphasized the need for sufficient training and pre-observation support to ensure teachers are comfortable with the technical and procedural requirements of the process.

It underscores that while classroom observation is a valuable mechanism for professional growth, it can inadvertently create stressors that impede authentic teaching performance. Supportive practices—such as pre-observation orientation, constructive feedback, and mentoring—are therefore critical to reducing anxiety and ensuring that classroom observation remains a developmental rather than punitive process (Zaare, 2012; Reños & Pontillas, 2024).

The findings imply that classroom observation, while essential for professional development, may create significant pressure on teachers due to time constraints and limited resources. This suggests the need for schools to provide adequate preparation time and accessible instructional resources so teachers can focus more on effective teaching rather than logistical demands.

The difficulty in lesson pacing indicates that teachers may benefit from support in designing flexible and realistic lesson plans for observation. Providing training on time management, lesson structuring, and adaptive teaching strategies can help teachers deliver content more confidently within limited time frames.

The presence of instructional pressure and performance anxiety highlights the importance of creating a supportive and non-threatening observation environment. School leaders and observers should emphasize formative, developmental feedback rather than evaluative judgment to help teachers feel more at ease and perform more authentically.

Emotional and psychological challenges suggest that teacher well-being should be a priority during the observation process. Establishing mentoring systems, peer support, and pre-observation orientations can help reduce anxiety and build teachers' confidence.

The findings also imply that observation practices should be reviewed to ensure alignment with actual classroom conditions. Allowing flexibility in instructional materials, teaching strategies, and technology use can help teachers demonstrate their genuine teaching practices rather than staged performances.

Overall, strengthening institutional support, improving observation systems, and promoting a culture of trust and professional growth can help transform classroom observation into a more meaningful and less stressful experience for teachers.

Table 6. Distribution of Challenges Encountered by Teachers During Classroom Observation

Statements	n=Frequency	Percentage	Rank
1. Preparing instructional materials within limited time or available resources	115	52%	1
2. Adjusting or shortening lesson activities to meet time expectations	103	47%	2

3. Maintaining fluency or confidence in the medium of instruction under pressure	99	45%	3	37
4. Maintaining composure and confidence throughout the observation	95	43%	4.5	
5. Managing feelings of pressure or anticipation regarding feedback	95	43%	4.5	
6. Managing learner behavior with added observation-related pressure	92	42%	6	
7. Managing limited time to revise lesson plans before the observation	89	40%	7	
8. Using visual aids or technology not typically part of everyday practice	41	19%	8	
9. Adjusting lesson plans to align with observer expectations	35	16%	9.5	
10. Conducting meaningful assessments within the time constraints of observation	35	16%	9.5	
11. Limiting the use of code-switching or informal language strategies during the session	33	15%	11	
12. Following the allotted time strictly while covering all parts of the lesson	30	14%	12	
13. Remaining focused despite concerns about language use or communication clarity	29	13%	13.5	
14. Teaching effectively despite being observed by supervisors or unfamiliar individuals	29	13%	13.5	
15. Providing feedback to learners effectively during observed lessons	28	13%	15.5	
16. Preparing lesson plans with more detail or structure than usual	28	13%	15.5	
17. Accessing appropriate or updated instructional materials when needed	26	12%	17.5	
18. Using formal assessment tools not regularly implemented in daily teaching	26	12%	17.5	
19. Making real-time classroom management decisions under observation	24	11%	19	
20. Modifying the usual pacing of the lesson to accommodate the observation	23	10%	20.5	
21. Observing changes in learner behavior due to the presence of an observer	23	10%	20.5	

The data is supported by conducting follow-up interviews with selected teachers' respondents after identifying the top five results from the questionnaire based on the frequency.

Table 6.1. Preparing instructional materials within limited time and available resources

Emerging Themes	Code	Participant Responded
6.1.1 Time Constraints and Workload	Limited time, competing tasks, short notice	TP 2, TP3, TP4, TP7, TP10
6.1.2 Resource Scarcity and Financial Limitations	Lack of materials, out-of-pocket expenses, limited resources	TP5, TP6, TP8, TP12, TP14
6.1.3 Unexpected Technical Problems	Technical issues, equipment failure	TP2, TP11, TP15, TP1, TP9

Legend: TP – Teachers’ Participant

Table 6.1 presents the emerging themes identified from the participants’ responses regarding the challenges in preparing instructional materials within limited time and available resources during classroom observations. The table categorizes these challenges into three emerging themes: Time Constraints and Workload, highlighting issues related to limited preparation time, competing tasks, and short notice; Resource Scarcity and Financial Limitations, which focuses on the lack of available teaching materials, the need for out-of-pocket expenses, and limited resources; and Unexpected Technical Problems, emphasizing difficulties caused by equipment failure or other technical issues. The corresponding participant respondents for each theme are also listed to indicate the sources of the data supporting these findings.

It implies that teachers’ ability to prepare effective instructional materials is strongly influenced by time availability, resource accessibility, and technical readiness. The presence of time constraints and heavy workload suggests the need for improved scheduling, advance notice of observations, and institutional support to allow sufficient preparation time. Resource scarcity and financial limitations highlight the importance of providing adequate school-based materials and funding support to reduce teachers’ out-of-pocket expenses. Meanwhile, unexpected technical problems indicate the necessity for reliable equipment, technical assistance, and contingency planning. Overall, strengthening administrative support systems, resource provision, and preparation policies can help teachers develop quality instructional materials despite operational limitations.

6.1.1 Time Constraints and Workload

The participants were asked how time constraints and workloads affect them during classroom observation. The participants responded and stated that:

Halos isang buong linggo ma-post mo ang lesson plan kasi kailangan mong insert doon lahat ng indicators na kailangang makita (TP2) (It can take almost a whole week to post the lesson plan because you need to include all the indicators that must be covered, TP2)

Minsan nagmamadali talaga kami sa paghahandaan ng materials... minsan kulang sa oras at resources. (TP3) (Sometimes we really rush to prepare the materials... sometimes there is not enough time and resources, TP3)

Lalo na kapag short notice ang observation... minsan one day before lang nasasabi, kaya ang hirap magprepare ng mga materials lalo na kung may klase ka pa buong araw. (TP4) (Especially when the observation is on short notice... sometimes we’re informed only a day before, so it’s hard to prepare the materials, especially when you still have classes all day, TP4)

Isa yan sa pinakamalaking challenge... aside sa teaching load, may extra duties pa kami kaya halos gabi na nakakagawa ng instructional materials. (TP7) (That is one of the biggest challenges... besides the teaching load, we have extra duties, so we often end up preparing instructional materials late at night, TP7)

Nakaka-stress minsan kasi gusto mo perfect lahat, lesson plan, materials, classroom set-up, pero limitado ang oras. Parang kulang lagi ang isang araw. (TP10) (It can be stressful because you want everything to be perfect—lesson plan, materials, classroom set-up—but the time is limited. It feels like a day is never enough, TP10)

Teachers often experience high pressure due to limited time, competing tasks, and short notice when preparing for classroom observations. Developing comprehensive lesson plans while balancing teaching and administrative duties requires significant effort, often extending into personal time. These challenges align with Archer et al. (2016), who emphasized that workload and time pressure can compromise lesson planning and teacher readiness during evaluations.

6.1.2 Resource Scarcity and Financial Limitations

The participants were asked how financial limitations impact their preparation of instructional materials during classroom observations, and they shared their experiences regarding the challenges of insufficient resources and out-of-pocket expenses. They responded and stated that:

Kadalasan kulang sa oras at minsan kulang din sa supplies... minsan out of pocket na namin kinukuha ang pambiling cartolina, ink, at iba pang materials para lang maganda ang output sa observation. (TP5) (Most of the time, we lack enough time and sometimes we also lack supplies... sometimes we even pay out of pocket to buy cartolina, ink, and other materials just to make the output look good for the observation, TP5)

Minsan gusto mong gumawa ng manipulative materials pero walang available na printer o colored ink kaya napipilitan na lang mag-simple visual aids. (TP6) (Sometimes you want to create manipulative materials, but when there's no available printer or colored ink, you're forced to just make simple visual aids, TP6)

Lalo na po kung may sabayang activities sa school gaya ng contests o programs. Napupuyat kami kakagawa ng mga visual aids at PowerPoint para lang maganda ang presentation sa observation. (TP8) (Especially when there are simultaneous activities in the school, like contests or programs. We stay up late making visual aids and PowerPoints just to make the presentation look good for the observation, TP8)

Minsan wala kaming enough support materials from the school. Minsan kailangan mo pa gumawa ng sarili mong charts, flashcards, at props. Kaya dagdag gastos at effort. (TP12) (Sometimes we don't have enough support materials from the school. Sometimes you even have to make your own charts, flashcards, and props. So, it adds more cost and effort, TP12)

Totoo sir, lalo na kung gusto mong interactive ang lesson mo. Kailangan mo ng printed materials, visuals, at minsan actual objects pa. Pero dahil limited ang time at budget, hindi lahat nagagawa. (TP14)
(That's true, sir, especially if you want your lesson to be interactive. You need printed materials, visuals, and sometimes even actual objects. But because of limited time and budget, not everything can be done, TP14)

Teachers often face challenges due to insufficient teaching materials and financial constraints. These limitations affect creativity and the ability to deliver high-quality, interactive lessons. This is consistent with Milenković (2024), who noted that inadequate resources can hinder teachers' lesson preparation and compromise instructional quality during classroom observations.

6.1.3 Unexpected Technical Problems

The participants were asked about the challenges they face with unexpected technical problems during classroom observations and stated that:

Minsan kahit na mag-prepare ka ng PowerPoint, naisip mo na baka mag-brown out... kailangan gagawa ka ng visual aids. Talagang piniprepare mo siya before ang time na demonstrationmo. (TP2)
(Even if you prepare a PowerPoint, you might think there could be a power outage... so you need to make visual aids. You really have to prepare them before your demonstration time, TP2)

Isa sa mga problema ko talaga ay ang availability ng materials. Halimbawa, gusto kong gumamit ng projector pero minsan sira o kaya reserved na ng ibang teacher. Kaya dapat may backup visual aids talaga. (TP11)
(One of my real problems is the availability of materials. For example, I want to use a projector, but sometimes it's broken or reserved by another teacher. So, you really need to have backup visual aids, TP11)

Minsan kahit maaga ka mag-prepare, may unexpected problems pa rin, printer error, brownout, o kulang ang supplies. Kaya kahit gusto mong best output, hindi talaga maiwasan ang limitations. (TP15)
(Even if you prepare early, unexpected problems still happen, like printer errors, power outages, or missing supplies. So even if you want the best output, these limitations are unavoidable, TP15)

Kailangan mo talagang mag doble effort since they affect the observers' impression. (TP1)
(You really have to double your effort since it affects the observers' impression, TP1)

Minsan kahit gust mong i-improve pa yung material mo, hindi na kaya sa oras. Kaya kung ano na lang ang kaya maihabol, yun na lang ang nagagamit. (TP9)
(Sometimes, even if you want to improve your materials, there's not enough time. So, you just use whatever you can finish in time, TP9)

Unexpected technical problems, such as equipment failure or power outages, create additional stress for teachers and may compromise the quality of instructional materials. Teachers must prepare contingency plans and extra effort to ensure lessons run smoothly. This supports findings by Granström et

al. (2024), who emphasized that technical challenges can impede lesson delivery and teacher performance during classroom observations

Table 6.2. Adjusting or Shortening Lesson Activities to Meet Time Expectations

Emerging Themes	Code	Participant Responded
6.2.1 Use of Timers and Activity Pacing	Guided instruction, timing, structured lesson flow	TP1, TP2, TP6, TP11, TP12
6.2.2 Prioritization of Core Content	Essential activities, lesson objectives, instructional focus	TP3, TP8, TP9, TP10, TP15
6.2.3 Flexibility and Adaptation in Lesson Delivery	Lesson adjustment, group modification, adaptive teaching	TP4, TP5, TP7, TP13, TP14

Legend: TP – Teachers' Participant

Table 6.2 presents the teachers' experiences in adjusting or shortening lesson activities to meet time expectations during classroom observations. The table identifies three emerging sub-themes—Use of Timers and Activity Pacing, Prioritization of Core Content, and Flexibility and Adaptation in Lesson Delivery—along with their corresponding codes, participant respondents, and selected responses. This highlights how teachers manage limited time, maintain instructional flow, and ensure learning objectives are achieved despite observational pressures.

It implies that effective lesson pacing and time management are essential competencies that help teachers maintain instructional flow while meeting observation expectations. The use of timers and structured pacing highlights the need for professional development in planning time-bound activities, while the prioritization of core content emphasizes the importance of curriculum literacy and objective-focused instruction to ensure essential learning outcomes are achieved despite limited time. Moreover, the teachers' flexibility and adaptation in lesson delivery demonstrate the value of adaptive teaching practices, suggesting that observation systems should recognize responsive instructional adjustments as indicators of professional competence and effective classroom management.

6.2.1 Use of Timers and Activity Pacing

The participants were asked how they manage lesson pacing and time allocation during classroom observations. They responded and stated that:

Imbes na full group activity, ginagawa kong pair work o individual para mabilis matapos. (TP3) (Instead of full group activity, I make it pair work or individual to finish faster, TP3)

Isa o dalawang grupo lang nakakapagpakita. Kaya minsan nagiging challenge talaga kung paano mo iha-handle ang oras. (TP8) (Only one or two groups get to present. Sometimes it's really a challenge to handle the time, TP8)

Pag observation, mahirap gawin yun kasi kailangan sundin yung prepared plan. (TP9) (During observation, it's hard to do because you need to follow the prepared plan, TP9)

Parang mechanical na yung teaching kasi lagi kang conscious sa oras. (TP10) (Teaching becomes mechanical because you are always conscious of time.)

Alam mo na kung alin ang dapat i-cut short at alin ang pwedeng i-extend. Experience na lang talaga. (TP15) (You learn which to cut short and which to extend. It's really experience. TP15)

Teachers actively use timers, time allocations, and quick transitions to manage limited time during classroom observations. This structured approach ensures lessons remain on track and prevents activities from running over time, highlighting the challenge of balancing thorough instruction with time constraints. According to Marzano (2024), effective time management is a key component of classroom efficiency, as it allows teachers to maximize instructional impact within restricted periods. Similarly, Myers (2012) emphasized that well-paced lessons promote student engagement and enable teachers to meet objectives without compromising learning quality, even under observation pressure.

6.2.2 Prioritization of Core Content

The participants were asked how they handle lesson delivery when time is limited, and they stated that:

May mga part ng activity na gusto ko sana ipagawa sa bata pero dahil may time limit kailangan ko na lang i-shortcut. (TP4) (There are parts of the activity I would like students to do, but because of time limits, I have to shortcut them, TP4)

Inuuna ko yung important parts at yung mga hindi kaya, nililipat ko na lang sa susunod na session. (TP5) (I prioritize the important parts and move what can't fit to the next session, TP5)

Kailangan mo talagang isakripisyo ang ilan sa mga activity para magkasya sa oras. Kaya minsan ang ginagawa ko, binibigyan ko na lang ng assignment or continuation task sa labas ng klase. (TP7) (You really need to sacrifice some activities to fit the time. Sometimes I give assignments or continuation tasks outside class, TP7)

Dahil may observer, kailangan mong bilisan. Kaya tinatanggap ko na lang na hindi lahat ng maganda sa plan ay magagawa sa oras na binigay. (TP13) (Because of the observer, you need to speed up. I accept that not everything good in the plan can be done in the given time, TP13)

Basta makuha ng bata ang core concept, okay na sa akin. (TP14) (As long as the student gets the core concept, it's okay with me, TP14)

Teachers must prioritize essential content to ensure learning objectives are met. Sacrificing non-essential parts or transferring them to assignments allows the lesson to remain focused and meaningful despite time limitations. This finding supports Myers (2012), who noted that effective time management in instruction requires teachers to distinguish between essential and supplementary content to maximize learning within limited periods. Similarly, Marzano (2024) emphasized that focusing on core learning goals enhances instructional efficiency and ensures that learners grasp fundamental concepts even under time constraints.

6.2.3 Flexibility and Adaptation in Lesson Delivery

The participants were asked about how they adjust their lesson delivery during classroom observations when faced with time constraints. They stated that:

Imbes na full group activity, ginagawa kong pair work o individual para mabilis matapos.

(Instead of full group activity, I make it pair work or individual to finish faster.)

Isa o dalawang grupo lang nakakapagpakita. Kaya minsan nagiging challenge talaga kung paano mo iha-handle ang oras.

(Only one or two groups get to present. Sometimes it's really a challenge to handle the time.)

Pag observation, mahirap gawin yun kasi kailangan sundin yung prepared plan. (During observation, it's hard to do because you need to follow the prepared plan.)

Parang mechanical na yung teaching kasi lagi kang conscious sa oras. Hindi mo na masyadong nae-enjoy yung actual interaction sa mga bata.

(Teaching becomes mechanical because you are always conscious of time. You don't enjoy the actual interaction with students as much.)

Alam mo na kung alin ang dapat i-cut short at alin ang pwedeng i-extend. Experience na lang talaga. (You learn which to cut short and which to extend. It's really experience.)

Teachers adapt their lessons by adjusting group work, pacing discussions, or modifying activities based on observation constraints. Experience and flexibility help them manage stress and maintain instructional flow, even under pressure. This is supported by Archer et al. (2016), who highlighted that experienced teachers develop adaptive strategies to handle time pressures and maintain lesson effectiveness. Similarly, Milenković (2024) emphasized that teacher flexibility and responsiveness are key to sustaining instructional quality during classroom observations and other evaluative settings.

Table 6.3. Maintaining Fluency or Confidence in the Medium of Instruction Under Pressure

Emerging Themes	Code	Participant Responded
6.3.1 Language Anxiety During Observation	Nervousness, fear of errors, self-consciousness	TP1, TP3, TP4, TP5, TP10
6.3.2 Strategic Language Adjustment	Use of mother tongue, simplified English	TP2, TP6, TP7, TP11, TP13
6.3.3 Confidence-Building Techniques	Practice, positive mindset, familiarity with content	TP8, TP9, TP12, TP14, TP15

Legend: TP – Teachers' Participant

Table 6.3 shows the teachers' challenges in maintaining fluency and confidence under observation. It highlights three themes: Language Anxiety, where teachers feel nervous and self-conscious; Strategic Language Adjustment, using mother tongue or simplified English for better student understanding; and Confidence-Building Techniques, relying on practice and preparation to stay composed.

It implies that teachers' fluency and confidence in the medium of instruction are significantly influenced by psychological pressure during observations. The presence of language anxiety suggests the need for supportive and non-threatening evaluation environments that reduce fear of errors and promote professional growth. The use of strategic language adjustments, such as integrating the mother tongue or simplifying English, highlights teachers' adaptive competence in ensuring learner comprehension despite pressure. Meanwhile, the emphasis on confidence-building techniques underscores the importance of preparation, content mastery, and positive mindset in strengthening instructional delivery. Overall, fostering supportive observation practices and providing language enhancement and confidence-building opportunities can help teachers maintain effective communication under evaluative conditions.

6.3.1 Language Anxiety During Observation

The participants were asked about their experiences maintaining fluency in the medium of instruction during classroom observations. They responded and stated that:

Oo lalo na kapag english ang medium of instruction, minsan kabado yung teacher lalo na kapag ang mga bata talagang magagaling nadin sa English lalo na sa generation nila, ayun kailangan mahusay Kadin talagang mag English.(TP1)(Yes, especially when English is the medium of instruction, teachers sometimes feel nervous, especially if the students are already proficient in English for their generation, so you really need to be good at English, TP1)

Kahit po prepared ako kapag nandiyan ang observer parang nabablangko ako minsan nahirapan ako minsan mag English straight. (TP3) (Even if I am prepared, when the observer is there, I sometimes blank out and struggle to speak English fluently, TP3)

Minsan okay naman, pero kapag alam mong may nanonood, mas nagiging conscious ka. Parang gusto mo lahat ng sinasabi mo perfect English, kaya nawawala yung natural na flow ng discussion. (TP4) (Sometimes it's okay, but when you know someone is watching, you become more self-conscious. You want everything you say to be perfect English, which disrupts the natural flow of the discussion, TP4)

Ako, kabisado ko na English lesson ko, pero kapag may principal or observer sa likod, parang iba yung kaba. Kaya minsan tinatagalog ko na lang ng konti kasi mas relaxed ako pag ganun. (TP5) (I know my English lessons well, but when a principal or observer is at the back, the nervousness feels different. So sometimes I switch to Tagalog a little because I feel more relaxed that way, TP5)

Ako kasi, sanay na mag-English sa klase, pero iba talaga pag formal observation. Kahit sanay ka, may kaba pa rin. Pero ang technique ko, iniisip ko na lang na normal class lang para hindi ako ma-tense. (TP10) (I am used to teaching in English, but it's different during a formal observation. Even if you're used to it, there's still nervousness. My technique is to just think of it as a normal class so I won't get tense, TP10)

Teachers experience heightened nervousness and anxiety when teaching in English under observation, affecting fluency and delivery. This aligns with findings by Zaare (2012), who noted that

teacher anxiety can significantly influence classroom performance and language use under evaluative conditions.

6.3.2 Strategic Language Adjustment

The participants were asked how they manage language use during classroom observations, and they stated that:

Siguro dito paano ba ito? Siguro kapag English... Minsan siguro naging problema rin doon sa student, kasi kahit na gawin mo, sabihin natin kahit pababain mo o pashallow mo ang English mo, pero kung di talaga maintindihan ng student talagang mapagamit ka talaga ng Tagalog o kung anong language mas maintindihan nila. (TP2) (Sometimes, even if you simplify your English, if the student doesn't understand, you really have to use Tagalog or another language they understand, TP2)

To be honest, di ko na masyado iniisip kung perfect yung grammar ko. Ang mahalaga, naiintindihan ng bata. Pero syempre, kapag observation, pinipilit ko rin na maging maayos ang English ko kahit kinakabahan. (TP6) (Honestly, I don't focus too much on perfect grammar. What matters is that the students understand. But of course, during observation, I also try to use proper English even if I'm nervous, TP6)

Depende rin sa topic. Kapag science or English subject talaga, confident ako. Pero sa MAPEH, minsan nahihirapan kasi iba ang mga terminologies. Kaya minsan halo-halo na yung English at Tagalog. (TP7) (It also depends on the topic. In science or English, I'm confident, but in MAPEH, it's sometimes difficult because of different terminology, so I mix English and Tagalog, TP7)

Minsan, kahit gusto mong English lang, bumabalik ka sa mother tongue kasi gusto mong mas maintindihan ng bata. Di mo rin naman pwedeng pilitin kung nahihirapan sila. (TP11) (Sometimes, even if you want to use only English, you switch to the mother tongue because you want the students to understand. You can't force it if they struggle, TP11)

Mahirap din pag tinatamad o tahimik ang bata. Parang awkward tuloy mag-English mag-isa. Kaya minsan sinisingitan ko ng Tagalog para maging alive ulit yung klase. (TP13) (It's hard when students are unresponsive or silent. Speaking English alone feels awkward, so sometimes I use Tagalog to make the class lively again, TP13)

Teachers employ strategic code-switching or simplified English to maintain comprehension while under observation. This supports Chiou (2023), who highlighted that teachers adapt language to suit student comprehension and reduce communication barriers during evaluative contexts.

6.3.3 Confidence-Building Techniques

The participants were asked how they maintain fluency and confidence under observation pressure, and they stated that:

Kapag English-speaking class, nakakahiya kapag nagkakamali ka sa grammar. Kaya minsan sobrang conscious ako. Pero kapag nakikita kong relaxed ang mga bata, doon ako bumabalik sa normal. (TP8) (In English-speaking classes, it’s embarrassing to make grammar mistakes. Sometimes I become too conscious. But when I see the students are relaxed, I return to normal, TP8)

Mahirap talaga kapag pressured. Parang kahit anong practice mo, pag nandiyon na ang observer, nag-iiba ang tono at bilis ng pagsasalita mo. Tapos kung minsan, mali-mali na rin. (TP9) (It’s really hard under pressure. No matter how much you practice, when the observer is there, your tone and pace change, and sometimes you make mistakes, TP9)

Ako, before mag-demo, pinapractice ko talaga magsalita sa harap ng salamin. Nakakatulong yun sa confidence. Pero pag andiyan na ang observer, kahit ganun, may kaba pa rin talaga. (TP12) (Before demonstrating, I practice speaking in front of the mirror. It helps my confidence. But when the observer is there, I still get nervous, TP12)

Kapag English, conscious ako pero nasasanay na rin. Sa una lang talaga yung kaba. Pag nakikita kong nakikinig ang observer na nakangiti, parang lumalakas loob ko. (TP14) (I’m conscious when speaking English, but I get used to it. The nervousness is only at first. When I see the observer listening and smiling, I gain confidence, TP14)

Sa akin, depende sa mood. Kapag kalmado ako, tuloy-tuloy lang English ko. Pero pag kabado, automatic lumalabas yung Tagalog kahit di ko sinasadya. (TP15) (For me, it depends on my mood. When I’m calm, my English flows smoothly, but when nervous, Tagalog automatically comes out even if I don’t intend it, TP15)

Teachers develop confidence-building strategies, such as practice, observing student cues, and maintaining a positive mindset, to cope with nervousness and maintain fluency. This aligns with Granström et al. (2024), who found that teacher self-efficacy and preparatory routines enhance performance under evaluative pressure.

Table 6.4. Maintaining Composure and Confidence Throughout the observation

Emerging Themes	Code	Participant Responded
6.4.1 Initial Nervousness and Anxiety	Nervousness, shakiness, tension	TP2, TP3, TP12
6.4.2 Coping Strategies During Observation	Smiling, deep breathing, mindset adjustment	TP4, TP5, TP6
6.4.3 Regaining Confidence Through Classroom Engagement	Focus on students, experience, positive mindset	TP8, TP9, TP10

Legend: TP - Teacher Participant

Table 6.4 presents how teachers maintain composure and confidence during classroom observations. It highlights the challenges of initial nervousness, coping mechanisms employed during the lesson, and strategies for regaining confidence through active classroom engagement.

The results in Table 6.4 imply that teachers commonly experience initial nervousness during classroom observations, which may affect early lesson delivery; however, the use of coping strategies such as deep breathing, positive mindset, and composure techniques helps them manage stress effectively. The results also indicate that active classroom engagement and focusing on learners enable teachers to gradually regain confidence as the lesson progresses. These implications highlight the importance of providing stress-management support, confidence-building training, and a supportive observation environment that encourages teachers to remain learner-focused despite evaluative pressures.

6.4.1 Initial Nervousness and Anxiety

The participants were asked about their experiences regarding nervousness at the start of classroom observations. They stated that teachers often feel anxious, shaky, and tense, particularly at the beginning, due to the presence of observers, technical concerns, or the fear of making mistakes.

Siguro sir challenge rin talaga siya. Una sa pag-umpisa pa lang, kinakabahan ka diba? Tapos manginignig-nginig ka. Tapos minsan nagkakaproblema ka pa sa powerpoint mo, hindi mag-compatible ang HDMI sa laptop sa TV. So kakabahan ka na, hindi ka na makakapag... Tapos minsan makakalimutan mo kung ano na nga yung susunod ko, mga ganoon. Talagang challenge talaga siya. (TP2) (It's really challenging, sir. At the start, you get nervous, shaking. Sometimes your PowerPoint doesn't work or HDMI isn't compatible, so you panic. Sometimes you forget your next step. It's really a challenge, TP2)

Nakakakaba talaga sir, ewan kahit ready ka mauutal-utal ka talaga sa nerbyus. (TP3) (It's really nerve-wracking, sir. Even if you're prepared, you might stammer because of nervousness, TP3)

Ako, inaamin ko, nanginiginig talaga ako sa simula. Pero pag tumagal, nasasanay ka na rin. Ang sikreto, huwag magmukhang tense kahit kinakabahan ka sa loob. (TP12) (I admit, I shake at the beginning. But as time passes, you get used to it. The key is not to show tension even if you're nervous inside, TP12)

Teachers experience high initial anxiety during observations, a finding supported by Chiou (2023), who noted that observation settings heighten teachers' self-consciousness and stress. These responses reflect the natural psychological impact of evaluation pressure, particularly when technology or lesson flow is uncertain.

6.4.2 Coping Strategies During Observation

The participants were asked how they manage their composure while teaching under observation. They responded and stated that:

Ako, ginagawa ko, ngumingiti lang kahit may mali akong masabi. Para di halata sa observer na nagkamali ako. Importante talaga na hindi ka mag-panic. (TP4) (I just smile even if I make a mistake. So, it's not obvious to the observer. It's really important not to panic, TP4)

Minsan, gusto mo nang kabahan pero iisipin mo na lang, normal class lang 'to. Yun na lang lagi kong mindset para hindi ako matense. (TP5)

(Sometimes you feel nervous, but I just think, this is a normal class. That's my mindset to stay relaxed. TP5)

Minsan tahimik ka na lang para hindi mo maipakita na natataranta ka. Hinga ka lang ng malalim tapos smile ulit. (TP6) (Sometimes you just stay quiet to hide that you're flustered. Take a deep breath and smile again, TP6)

Teachers employ practical coping strategies to maintain composure, aligning with Myers (2012) who suggested that maintaining professionalism under observation often relies on self-regulation, positive mindset, and stress management techniques. These strategies help sustain instructional quality despite internal pressure.

6.4.3 Regaining Confidence Through Classroom Engagement

The participants were asked how they regain confidence during the lesson. They stated that:

May time na muntik na akong maiyak kasi nagloko ang PowerPoint ko. Pero pinilit kong tumawa at idiretso pa rin sa discussion. Sabi nga nila, show must go on. (TP8) (There were times I almost cried because my PowerPoint malfunctioned. But I forced myself to laugh and continue with the discussion. As they say, the show must go on, TP8)

Kapag andiyan na talaga ang observers, parang lahat ng ginagawa mo may pressure. Pero kapag nasimulan ko na at nakikita kong nag-eejoy ang mga bata, doon bumabalik yung confidence ko. (TP9) (When observers are present, everything feels pressured. But once I start and see the students enjoying, my confidence comes back, TP9)

Mahirap talaga i-maintain yung composure pero nagagawa mo rin pag nasanay ka. Confidence din kasi natututunan yan sa experience. (TP10) (It's hard to maintain composure, but you can do it with practice. Confidence is something learned through experience, TP10)

Teachers rebuild confidence by focusing on student responses and leveraging experience, consistent with Granström et al. (2024) who emphasized that classroom engagement and prior teaching experience mitigate anxiety during observation. These findings highlight the dynamic interplay between teacher composure and active classroom interaction.

Table 6.5. Managing Feelings of Pressure or Anticipation Regarding Feedback

Emerging Themes	Code	Participant Responded
6.5.1 Anxiety and Nervousness Prior to Feedback	Nervousness, fear of judgment, self-consciousness	TP1, TP2, TP4, TP6, TP9
6.5.2 Balancing Positive and Negative Emotions	Excitement, fear, relief, disappointment	TP3, TP5, TP7, TP8, TP10
6.5.3 Feedback as an Opportunity for Growth	Reflection, improvement, continuous learning	TP11, TP12, TP13, TP14, TP15

Legend: TP – Teachers' Participant

Table 6.5 presents how teachers experience pressure and anticipation during feedback sessions after classroom observations. It highlights emotional responses ranging from anxiety to viewing feedback as a learning opportunity, showing the balance between personal expectations and professional growth.

Table 6.5 implies that teachers experience mixed emotional responses toward observation feedback, with anxiety and anticipation often present prior to receiving evaluations. This highlights the need for constructive, supportive, and growth-oriented feedback practices that reduce fear of judgment and encourage professional reflection. The results also suggest that when feedback is framed as an opportunity for improvement, teachers are more likely to view the process positively and engage in continuous professional learning. Therefore, observation systems should emphasize developmental feedback approaches that foster emotional support, reflective practice, and sustained instructional improvement.

6.5.1 Anxiety and Nervousness Prior to Feedback

The participants were asked about how they feel before receiving feedback, and they stated that nervousness, fear of judgment, and self-consciousness often accompany the anticipation:

Oo kasi syempre pag mga feedback na yan talagang, ay nagkamali ako hindi ko nasabi ang dapat kong sabihin, so ang pressure doon ay sana hindi napansin, ganun. (TP1) (Yes, of course, especially during feedback, if I made a mistake or didn't say what I should, the pressure is that I hope it wasn't noticed, TP1)

Nakakakaba lalo na kapag alam mo sa sarili mo na mayroon kang mga pagkakamali talaga o may nakalimutan ka na i-present o ganoon sa flow ng iyong list. (TP2) (It's nerve-wracking, especially when you know you made mistakes or forgot to present some parts in the flow of your lesson, TP2)

Para sa akin, feedback ay double-edged. Gusto mo marinig kasi makakatulong, pero at the same time, natatakot ka rin. (TP4) (For me, feedback is double-edged. You want to hear it because it helps, but at the same time, you're scared, TP4)

Naku sir kapag alam mong formal observation, parang mas mabigat yung feedback. Kaya habang nagtuturo pa lang, iniisip mo na kung ano sasabihin nila. Nakaka-distract minsan pero parte na talaga ng proseso.

(TP6) (Oh sir, during formal observation, feedback feels heavier. Even while teaching, you're already thinking about what they'll say. It can be distracting, but it's part of the process, TP6)

May time na nagkamali ako ng part sa lesson, tapos habang nagfe-feedback si MT namin, parang ayoko na tumingin. (TP9) (There were times I made a mistake in the lesson, and while our MT was giving feedback, I didn't want to look, TP9)

Teachers reported feeling pressured when anticipating feedback, especially if they feared mistakes or overlooked content during the lesson. This anxiety aligns with the concept of performance evaluation stress, where observation increases self-consciousness (Chiou, 2023; Granström et al., 2024). Participant 1 shared, "Oo kasi syempre pag mga feedback na yan talagang, ay nagkamali ako hindi ko nasabi ang dapat kong sabihin, so ang pressure doon ay sana hindi napansin..." ("Yes, especially when it comes to feedback, if I made a mistake or didn't say what I should have, the pressure is that I hope it wasn't noticed"). Similarly, Participant 2 admitted that graded observations intensify the nervousness despite regular teaching practice.

This theme underscores how feedback anticipation affects teacher composure and initial perception of their performance.

6.5.2 Balancing Positive and Negative Emotions

The participants were asked about the emotional tension experienced during feedback, and they stated that feedback evokes both excitement and apprehension:

Isa pa yang feedback sir, syempre iisipin mo nanaman kung ano ung gagawin mo sa mga susunod na demo. (TP3) (Feedback again, sir, you think about what you'll do in your next demo, TP3)

Minsan, kabado ako kasi alam kong may mga bagay akong hindi nagawa perfectly. Pero pinapaalala ko sa sarili ko na okay lang, feedback naman yan para sa growth, hindi para husgahan. (TP5) (Sometimes I get nervous because I know there are things I didn't do perfectly. But I remind myself it's okay, feedback is for growth, not judgment, TP5)

Ako sir, kinakabahan talaga pag sinasabing magbibigay na ng feedback. Pero pag narinig ko na puro positive naman, doon lang ako nakakahinga nang maluwag. (TP7) (I really get nervous when feedback is about to be given. But when I hear it's mostly positive, I can finally breathe, TP7)

Minsan sir di ko alam kung matatakot ba ako o ma-excite. Kasi feedback means improvement, pero syempre gusto mo rin marinig na maayos ang ginawa mo. (TP8) (Sometimes, sir, I don't know if I should be scared or excited. Feedback means improvement, but of course, you also want to hear that what you did was good, TP8)

Ako sir, nagiging emotional minsan. Kasi pag pinagpuyatan mo yung lesson mo tapos may mapuna pa rin, parang nakakadismaya. Pero at least alam mo kung ano babaguhin mo next time. (TP10) (Sometimes I get emotional. Because if you've spent long hours on your lesson and there's still criticism, it's a bit disappointing. But at least you know what to improve next time, TP10)

Teachers experience a dual emotional response, viewing feedback as helpful yet intimidating. These findings correspond with Archer et al. (2016), highlighting that teachers' emotional regulation is essential in professional evaluations to transform anxiety into constructive reflection.

6.4.3 Feedback as an Opportunity for Growth

The participants were asked how they view feedback after receiving it, and they stated that feedback is a tool for reflection, improvement, and continuous learning:

Minsan positive naman ang feedback pero nai-stress pa rin ako bago ito ibigay. Yung anticipation pa lang, parang exam na hindi mo alam kung pasado ka. (TP11) (Sometimes the feedback is positive, but I still get stressed before it's given. Just the anticipation feels like an exam where you don't know if you'll pass, TP11)

Ako, nasanay na rin. Dati super kabado ako pero ngayon tinitingnan ko na lang as opportunity. Kasi kung puro good feedback lang, hindi ka rin

matututo. (TP12) (I'm used to it now. I used to be very nervous, but now I see it as an opportunity. If it were only good feedback, you wouldn't learn, TP12)

Hindi talaga mawawala yung kaba. Kahit ilang beses ka na magpa-observe, pagdating sa feedback, parang first time ulit. (TP13) (The nervousness never really goes away. No matter how many times you're observed, feedback feels like the first time again, TP13)

Pag alam kong nagawa ko lahat, confident ako. Pero kapag may lapses, kahit maliit lang, yun ang iniisip ko buong araw bago ko pa marinig yung feedback. (TP14) (When I know I did everything, I'm confident. But if there were lapses, even small ones, I think about them all day before I hear the feedback, TP14)

Para sa akin, normal lang ma-pressure. Ang mahalaga, marunong kang tumanggap ng feedback at i-apply yun sa susunod. Yun naman talaga ang goal, continuous improvement. (TP15) (For me, feeling pressure is normal. What matters is knowing how to accept feedback and apply it next time. That's the real goal: continuous improvement, TP15)

Despite pressure, teachers acknowledge feedback as essential for reflection and professional development. This resonates with Marzano (2024), highlighting that reflective practice enhances teaching efficacy. Teachers' challenges during classroom observations reveals a complex interplay of challenges and adaptive strategies. Teachers reported significant difficulties in preparing instructional materials due to limited time, heavy workloads, insufficient resources, financial constraints, and unexpected technical problems such as equipment failure or power outages. Short-notice observations and overlapping duties often extended preparation into personal time, while resource scarcity forced teachers to simplify materials or spend out-of-pocket for visual aids, reinforcing findings by Archer et al. (2016) and Milenković (2024) on the impact of workload and resource limitations on instructional quality. To manage time pressures during lessons, teachers employed strategies such as pacing activities with timers, prioritizing core content, and flexibly adjusting group work or lesson delivery, ensuring that essential learning objectives were met despite observational constraints. This aligns with Myers (2012) and Marzano (2024), who emphasized the importance of effective time management and focusing on core learning goals to maintain instructional efficiency. Language use also emerged as a source of stress, with teachers experiencing nervousness when teaching in English, leading them to employ strategic code-switching or simplified language to maintain student comprehension, as noted by Chiou (2023) and Zaare (2012). Confidence-building techniques, including rehearsal, student engagement, and positive mindset, further helped teachers cope with observation pressures, supporting Granström et al. (2024) on the role of self-efficacy and preparatory routines. Additionally, anticipation of feedback elicited anxiety, mixed emotions, and heightened self-consciousness, yet teachers reframed these experiences as opportunities for reflection and professional growth, consistent with Archer et al. (2016) and Marzano (2024). Overall, while classroom observations generate stress and performance pressure, teachers demonstrate resilience through adaptive strategies, reflective practices, and skillful management of instructional and emotional demands, ultimately enhancing teaching effectiveness and professional development.

These findings imply that classroom observations, while stressful, can serve as valuable opportunities for professional growth when teachers are supported in managing instructional and emotional demands. Adaptive strategies such as time management, flexible lesson delivery, strategic language use, and confidence-building techniques not only help teachers cope with observation pressures but also enhance

teaching effectiveness. The results highlight the need for observation systems that are realistic, context-sensitive, and supportive, as well as professional development programs that strengthen teachers' coping skills, reflective practices, and resourcefulness. Ultimately, fostering such an environment can improve both teacher performance and student learning outcomes.

Coping Mechanisms Employed by the Teachers' Respondents to address the challenges they encounter during classroom observation?

Table 7 revealed that the most common coping strategies among teachers were preparing lesson plans well in advance and organizing the classroom environment to reduce distractions, both ranked first with a frequency of 117 and a percentage of 53%. These were followed by preparing backup activities in case of time shortage, which ranked third with a frequency of 116 and a percentage of 53%. Ranking fourth was using technology or visual aids they are comfortable with, which had a frequency of 102 and a percentage of 46%. Lastly, staying calm through breathing exercises or mindfulness and adjusting language use to balance formality and clarity both shared the fifth rank, each with a frequency of 101 and a percentage of 46%. These results indicate that teachers prioritize advance preparation, classroom management, and emotional regulation as vital coping mechanisms to sustain confidence and effectiveness during classroom observations.

The results show that teachers primarily rely on proactive and organized strategies, such as preparing lesson plans and instructional materials in advance and ensuring that the classroom environment is conducive to focused learning. Many respondents also demonstrate adaptability by preparing backup activities, using familiar technologies or visual aids, and carefully planning transitions to maintain lesson flow. Emotional regulation techniques, including mindfulness and breathing exercises, are commonly used to reduce anxiety and sustain composure during observations. Teachers also employ reflective and collaborative approaches, such as seeking advice from colleagues, reviewing past feedback, and drawing insights from prior experiences to improve their performance. Overall, these coping mechanisms show teachers' resilience and professionalism, emphasizing their capacity to balance preparation, adaptability, and self-regulation to ensure effective teaching even under evaluative conditions.

Research consistently shows that proactive preparation and organization are among the most effective strategies educators use to manage the pressures of being observed. According to Zaare (2012), teachers who prepare lesson plans and instructional materials in advance demonstrate greater confidence and classroom control, which helps mitigate anxiety associated with observation. Similarly, Archer et al. (2016) emphasized that well-prepared teachers can maintain lesson flow more effectively, as preparedness allows them to anticipate possible classroom challenges and respond flexibly to unexpected situations.

Adaptability also emerges as a key component of effective coping. Bhebhe and Nxumalo (2015) found that teachers who develop contingency plans or backup activities are better able to sustain student engagement, even when technical issues or time constraints arise. Chiou (2023) further noted that adaptability enhances teachers' capacity to use available technologies and visual aids efficiently, ensuring that instruction remains smooth and goal-oriented despite external pressures. These proactive measures not only improve instructional delivery but also foster a sense of control, which reduces performance-related stress.

Emotional regulation plays an equally vital role in managing the psychological demands of observation. Marzaini et al. (2024) highlighted that teachers often employ mindfulness, positive self-talk, and breathing techniques to maintain composure and focus during observed lessons. These self-regulatory strategies are closely linked to emotional intelligence, which allows teachers to manage anxiety and project confidence even under evaluative scrutiny (Granström et al., 2024). Myers (2012) also observed that emotional resilience directly contributes to teachers' ability to think clearly and respond constructively to classroom dynamics during stressful observation periods.

Reflective and collaborative coping strategies further strengthen teachers' professional growth. Reños and Pontillas (2024) reported that educators who engage in peer discussions, review feedback, and reflect on past observation experiences tend to demonstrate continuous improvement in teaching practices. Collaboration with colleagues fosters shared learning and reduces the sense of isolation often felt during evaluations. Likewise, Thom (2020) noted that mentorship and collegial advice help teachers translate feedback into actionable improvements, reinforcing their confidence and competence.

It supports the view that teachers' coping mechanisms—ranging from proactive planning to emotional regulation and collaborative reflection—demonstrate professionalism and resilience. These strategies not only reduce anxiety but also enhance instructional effectiveness, ensuring that classroom observations serve as opportunities for growth rather than sources of distress (Sugot & Ladia, 2024; Zaare, 2012).

Table 7. The Coping Mechanisms Teachers' Employ to Address the Challenges they Encounter During Classroom Observation?

Statements	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
1. Preparing lesson plans well in advance	117	53%	1.5
2. Organizing classroom environment to reduce distractions	117	53%	1.5
3. Preparing backup activities in case of time shortage	116	53%	3
4. Using technology or visual aids comfortable with	102	46%	4
5. Staying calm through breathing exercises or mindfulness	101	46%	5.5
6. Adjusting language use to balance formality and clarity	101	46%	5.5
7. Rehearsing transitions between lesson parts	49	22%	7
8. Managing time carefully to meet lesson expectations	44	20%	8.5
9. Practicing voice modulation and clarity	44	20%	8.5
10. Seeking support or advice from master teachers or colleagues	43	20%	10.5
11. Setting personal goals for each observation	43	20%	10.5
12. Reflecting on previous teaching experiences	41	19%	12
13. Practicing the lesson multiple times before the observation	38	17%	13.5
14. Reviewing past observation feedback for guidance	38	17%	13.5
15. Collaborating with co-teachers for peer review	37	17%	15
16. Using familiar instructional materials and techniques	35	16%	16
17. Building confidence through prior classroom experience	34	15%	17
18. Focusing on student engagement rather than observers	31	14%	18
19. Accepting feedback constructively and using it for improvement	29	13%	19

To better understand how teachers cope with the challenges they encounter during classroom observations, the researcher conducted a follow-up interview after identifying the top five coping strategies from the questionnaire results based on frequency and percentage. This part of the study aimed to gather personal insights on how teachers manage stress, time constraints, and the pressure to perform in front of observers. Before each interview, the researcher explained the purpose of the discussion and assured participants that their responses would remain confidential.

Table 7.1. Preparing Lesson Plans Well in Advance

Emerging Themes	Code	Participant Responded
7.1.1 Proactive Planning and Organization	Early preparation, revising, checking with master teachers, materials readiness	TP1, TP4, TP5, TP15
7.1.2 Emotional Readiness and Stress Management	Reducing anxiety, building confidence, peace of mind, avoiding panic	TP9, TP10, TP14

Legend: TP – Teachers' Participant

Table 7.1 presents the emerging themes identified from teachers' coping mechanism of preparing lesson plans well in advance. Two main themes emerged such as, Proactive Planning and Organization, which highlights early preparation, repeated revision, consultation with master teachers, and readiness of materials, and Emotional Readiness and Stress Management, which emphasizes reducing anxiety, building confidence, and maintaining peace of mind during classroom observations.

It implies that preparing lesson plans well in advance strengthens both instructional readiness and emotional stability among teachers. Proactive planning and organization enable teachers to refine lesson content, ensure material preparedness, and align instruction with expected standards, thereby improving lesson quality. At the same time, early preparation contributes to emotional readiness by reducing anxiety, building confidence, and minimizing last-minute pressure. These results highlight the importance of encouraging advance planning practices and providing planning support systems that promote both instructional effectiveness and teacher well-being during classroom observations.

7.1.1 Proactive Planning and Organization

The participants were asked how they handle the emotional demands of classroom observations. Many explained that their emotional readiness is closely linked to the proactive planning discussed in 7.1.1. By preparing lesson plans well in advance and they responded and stated that:

Syempre kailangan talaga advance kasi ipapacheck mo yan sa master teacher mo, kung okay ba yung mga pinaslak mo doong mga ano diba, activities and approaches. (TP1) (Of course, it really needs to be done in advance because you have to have it checked by your master teacher to see if what you included there, such as activities and approaches, are okay, TP1)

Usually one week before, tapos paulit-ulit kong nire-revise. Ayoko kasi na cramming, lalo na kung may observers. (TP4) (Usually I prepare one week before, and then I revise it repeatedly. I don't like cramming, especially when there are observers, TP4)

Advance planning talaga. Kaya dapat prepared na lahat ng materials, visuals, pati backup plan. (TP5) (Advance planning is really important. That's why all materials, visuals, and even backup plans should be ready. TP5)

Tinatapos ko agad yung lesson plan para maipa-check ko na. Para kung may kulang, maayos agad at hindi na magmamadali. (TP15) (I finish the lesson plan immediately so I can have it checked. That way, if something is missing, it can be fixed right away and I won't have to rush, TP15)

Teachers view proactive planning as essential for effective classroom management during observations. Early preparation allows them to revise, organize materials, and coordinate with master

teachers, minimizing last-minute stress and ensuring smooth lesson delivery. Proactive planning serves both practical and professional functions. It enables teachers to address gaps in content, organize activities efficiently, and meet observation expectations. This strategy promotes confidence, reduces errors, and enhances professional accountability

7.1.2 Emotional Readiness and Stress Management

The participants were asked how they cope with the emotional demands of classroom observations. The participants responded and stated that:

Maaga ko talaga ginagawa kasi ayoko na magpanic. At least kapag maayos na, makakafocus ako sa delivery sa mismong observation (TP9) (I really do it early because I don't want to panic. At least when it's all ready, I can focus on delivering the lesson during the observation, TP9)

Planning ahead gives me peace of mind. Alam kong ready ako, kaya kahit may konting kaba, manageable pa rin (TP10) (Planning ahead gives me peace of mind. I know I am ready, so even if I feel a little nervous, it's still manageable, TP10)

Minsan nagkakaroon ako ng kaba kahit prepared na ako. Pero malaking tulong talaga kapag maaga kang naghanda (TP14) (Sometimes I still feel nervous even if I'm prepared. But it really helps when you have prepared early, TP14)

Proactive planning directly contributes to emotional readiness. Preparing in advance helps teachers manage anxiety, maintain composure, and feel confident during classroom observations. This finding aligns with Marzano (2024), who emphasized that effective lesson preparation reduces uncertainty and boosts a teacher's sense of control during instructional delivery. Likewise, Thom (2020) noted that teachers who engage in systematic planning tend to experience less stress and greater self-efficacy, as preparedness fosters a calm and focused mindset in high-pressure situations such as classroom observations.

Emotional readiness and stress management are closely intertwined with proactive planning. Teachers who plan early report higher confidence and lower anxiety, showing that preparation is both a technical and psychological coping strategy that supports performance and professional composure. Milenković (2024) further supports this by asserting that emotional regulation among teachers is strengthened through pre-lesson organization and rehearsal, which minimize distractions and mental overload. Similarly, Myers (2012) found that the anticipation of being observed heightens stress levels, but this can be mitigated when teachers feel adequately prepared and supported through clear planning and feedback structures.

Table 7.2. Organizing Classroom Environment to Reduce Distractions

Emerging Themes	Code	Participant Responded
7.2.1 Classroom Arrangement and Seating Organization	arrangement, cleaning, placement of materials, ensuring presentable classroom	TP1, TP2, TP3, TP4, TP7
7.2.2 Visual Appeal and Environment	Controlled Minimal distractions, managing noise, appropriate decorations	TP1, TP2, TP4, TP5, TP7

Legend: TP – Teachers' Participant

The table presents the emerging themes that highlight how teachers organize their classrooms to minimize distractions during classroom observations. Table 7.2 implies that a well-organized and visually

controlled classroom environment plays a significant role in minimizing distractions and supporting effective teaching and learning. Proper classroom arrangement, cleanliness, and systematic placement of materials help create an orderly atmosphere that enhances instructional flow, while maintaining an appropriate visual appeal and managing noise levels promotes learner focus and engagement. These results highlight the importance of encouraging classroom organization practices and providing guidance on environment management to improve both teaching effectiveness and observation readiness.

7.2.1 Classroom Arrangement and Organization

The participants were asked how they organize their classrooms to minimize distractions and create a conducive learning environment during classroom observations. They responded and stated that:

Oo, syempre sa classroom observation dapat talaga well-organized lalo na kasama din yan kung paano ka iobserve, para may impact din sya doon ay ano ba yan, dapat maganda ang classroom mo (TP1) (Yes, of course, during classroom observation, the classroom must be well-organized, especially since it affects how you are observed. It should make a positive impact, so your classroom needs to look good, TP1)

Kailangan talaga, piniprepay po talaga, inaayos po ahead of time ang place po, ang classroom. Oo. Opo sir. Ano na po yan minsan kapag marami ang studyante tapos ganoon talaga sa atin marami ang studyante tapos ang liit lang ang classroom (TP2) (It really is necessary; I prepare it ahead of time and arrange the classroom. Sometimes when there are many students, and our classrooms are small, proper preparation becomes even more important, TP2)

Madalas ko man itong ginagawa sir, bale naka-ayos kaagad based doon sa activities na ipapagawa ko sa mga bata (TP3) (I usually do this, sir. I arrange the classroom immediately based on the activities I plan for the students, TP3)

Simple lang po ginagawa ko, sir. Nilalagay ko lang sa gilid ang mga gamit na di kailangan tapos pinapaupo ko nang maayos ang mga bata. Minsan kasi madaldal sila lalo na pag excited (TP4) (I just do something simple, sir. I put unnecessary materials aside and seat the students properly. Sometimes they talk a lot, especially when excited, TP4)

Bago pa mag-observe, pinapalinisan ko na talaga yung buong room. Kahit sa mga sulok, sir, kasi minsan napapansin din yun ng mga observer lalo na kung detalyado sila (TP7) (Before an observation, I really clean the whole room, even the corners, because sometimes observers notice those details, TP7)

The responses reveal that teachers prioritize classroom arrangement and organization to reduce distractions during observations. They employ strategies such as cleaning, arranging seats according to activities, minimizing unnecessary clutter, and preparing the environment ahead of time. These actions help maintain students' focus, ensure smooth lesson delivery, and create a positive impression during classroom observations.

Teachers consider the visual appeal and controlled environment of the classroom, ensuring it is pleasant but not overdecorated. They also address noise control and seating placement to manage student behavior effectively. This finding aligns with Zaare (2012), who emphasized that a well-organized and structured classroom environment enhances both teaching efficiency and student engagement, particularly during formal observations. Similarly, Archer et al. (2016) noted that environmental readiness reflects a teacher's professional competence, as it demonstrates their ability to create conditions conducive to effective learning.

Organizing the classroom demonstrates a proactive coping strategy that addresses both practical and environmental challenges during classroom observations. Proper arrangement, cleaning, and strategic placement of materials allow teachers to control distractions, manage student engagement, and maintain focus. Bhebhe and Nxumalo (2015) also found that teachers who maintain orderly learning spaces tend to perform better under observation because the environment supports instructional flow and minimizes external stressors.

Visual appeal and environmental management further enhance the classroom's conduciveness for teaching while reflecting the teacher's professionalism. According to Marzaini et al. (2024), creating a visually stimulating yet controlled classroom helps sustain learner attention and reinforces the teacher's confidence during observed sessions. By balancing functionality, aesthetics, and student management, teachers can confidently conduct lessons under observation, showing that environmental preparation is both a technical and psychological strategy for success.

7.2.2 Visual Appeal and Controlled Environment

The participants were asked how they manage the visual and environmental aspects of their classrooms to reduce distractions and create a conducive learning space during classroom observations. They responded and stated that:

Oo, syempre sa classroom observation dapat talaga well-organized lalo na kasama din yan kung paano ka iobserve, para may impact din sya doon ay ano ba yan, dapat maganda ang classroom mo (TP1) (Yes, of course, during classroom observation, the classroom must be well-organized, especially since it affects how you are observed. It should make a positive impact, so your classroom needs to look good, TP1)

Kailangan talaga, piniprepay po talaga, inaayos po ahead of time ang place po, ang classroom. Oo. Opo sir. Ano na po yan minsan kapag marami ang studyante tapos ganoon talaga sa atin marami ang studyante tapos ang liit lang ang classroom (TP2) (It really is necessary; I prepare it ahead of time and arrange the classroom. Sometimes when there are many students, and our classrooms are small, proper preparation becomes even more important, TP2)

Simple lang po ginagawa ko, sir. Nilalagay ko lang sa gilid ang mga gamit na di kailangan tapos pinapaupo ko nang maayos ang mga bata. Minsan kasi madaldal sila lalo na pag excited (TP4) (I just do something simple, sir. I put unnecessary materials aside and seat the students properly. Sometimes they talk a lot, especially when excited, TP4)

Ako sir, gusto ko talaga yung may konting decoration, parang may life yung classroom. Pero dapat hindi sobra kasi baka yun pa ang maka-distract

(TP5) (I want a little decoration, so the classroom feels lively. But it shouldn't be too much because it could become a distraction, TP5)

Bago pa mag-observe, pinapalinisan ko na talaga yung buong room. Kahit sa mga sulok, sir, kasi minsan napapansin din yun ng mga observer lalo na kung detalyado sila (TP7) (Before an observation, I really clean the whole room, even the corners, because sometimes observers notice those details, TP7)

The responses indicate that teachers view visual appeal and environmental control as critical components of classroom management during observations. They carefully arrange the space, manage noise, and limit decorations to avoid distracting students while creating a professional and inviting learning environment. These strategies help maintain focus, improve learner engagement, and ensure smooth lesson delivery.

Creating a visually appealing and controlled classroom reflects a proactive strategy that addresses both aesthetic and behavioral aspects of teaching. Teachers balance decoration with functionality, ensuring the environment supports concentration rather than becoming a source of distraction. This aligns with Zaare (2012), who emphasized that a well-structured and visually balanced classroom enhances student engagement and learning outcomes. Archer et al. (2016) also noted that environmental preparation demonstrates teacher professionalism and readiness, which positively affects observation outcomes. By managing visual elements and minimizing disruptions, teachers not only maintain students' focus but also increase their own confidence, showing that environmental management serves as both a pedagogical and psychological coping strategy.

Table 7.3. Preparing Backup Activities in Case of Time Shortage

Emerging Themes	Code	Participant Responded
7.3.1 Contingency Planning	Preparing alternative activities, Plan B, adaptable lesson flow	TP1, TP2, TP4, TP6, TP8
7.3.2 Classroom Flexibility and Readiness	Quick adjustment, handling technical issues, time management	TP3, TP5, TP7, TP9, TP10

Legend: TP – Teachers' Participant

The table presents the emerging themes related to how teachers prepare backup activities in case of time shortage during classroom observations. The first theme, Contingency Planning, highlights teachers' efforts to prepare alternative activities, maintain a Plan B, and adapt the lesson flow as needed, ensuring continuity of instruction. The second theme, Classroom Flexibility and Readiness, emphasizes teachers' ability to quickly adjust to unforeseen situations, handle technical issues, and manage time effectively, reflecting their preparedness and resilience in maintaining smooth classroom operations.

The findings in Table 7.3 imply that preparing backup activities strengthens teachers' instructional readiness and ensures continuity of learning despite time shortages or unexpected disruptions. Contingency planning allows teachers to maintain lesson objectives through alternative tasks, while classroom flexibility and quick adjustment skills enable effective responses to technical issues and pacing challenges. These results highlight the importance of promoting adaptive lesson planning and time-management training to support consistent instructional delivery during classroom observations.

7.3.1 Contingency Planning

The participants were asked how they prepare for unexpected events or time shortages during classroom observations. They stated that:

Ay opo sir! Talaga always dapat may back up kasi nangyari na bayan sa akin, Mabuti lang talaga at ready ako that time (TP3) (Yes, sir! You should always have a backup because it once happened to me, and I was really glad I was ready at that time, TP3)

Ako po, sir; minsan nagpi-print ako ng mga simplified activity sheets. Kung sakaling magkulang sa oras, at least may madaliang task pa rin ang mga bata (TP5) (Sometimes, sir, I print simplified activity sheets. If time runs out, the students at least still have a quick task to do, TP5)

Depende rin po sa lesson, sir. Pero kadalasan, may nakahanda akong short drill o review question kapag nakita kong may oras pa o may part na di natapos (TP7) (It depends on the lesson, sir. But usually, I have a short drill or review question ready if I see that there is extra time or some parts were not finished, TP7)

Oo sir, lalo na pag may observation. Dapat ready ka sa lahat ng pwedeng mangyari, brownout, laptop issue, o kahit kabahan ka man (TP9) (Yes, sir, especially during observation. You must be ready for anything that could happen, brownouts, laptop issues, or even if you feel nervous, TP9)

Hindi po ako umaalis nang walang backup. Kahit simpleng writing activity lang, nilalagay ko sa folder ko para kung may short time, may magagawa pa rin ang mga bata

(TP10) (I never leave without a backup. Even a simple writing activity is placed in my folder so that if there's little time, the students can still do something, TP10)

Teachers demonstrate flexibility and readiness by preparing short drills, simplified tasks, and quick alternatives to adjust to time limitations or unexpected events. This flexibility allows them to maintain the flow of the lesson and manage student engagement even under pressure. Time management and adaptability are key components of classroom resilience, ensuring that learning continues effectively despite challenges.

Classroom flexibility and readiness are essential coping strategies that complement contingency planning. Literature supports that teachers who can adapt quickly to changing circumstances maintain instructional quality and student engagement. Bibon (2022) notes that adaptability reduces stress and helps teachers respond effectively to technical issues or lesson overruns. Granström et al. (2024) further emphasize that flexible planning increases teacher confidence and performance during observations. By preparing for both predictable and unpredictable scenarios, teachers demonstrate professional competence and resilience, ensuring that learning objectives are met even when challenges arise.

7.3.2 Classroom Flexibility and Readiness

The participants were asked how they adjust their teaching and manage classroom activities when faced with unexpected situations or time constraints during classroom observations. They responded and stated that:

Ay opo sir! Talaga always dapat may back up kasi nangyari na bayan sa akin. (TP3) (Yes, sir! You should always have a backup because it once happened to me, TP3)

Ako po, sir; minsan nagpi-print ako ng mga simplified activity sheets. Kung sakaling magkulang sa oras, at least may madaliang task pa rin ang mga bata (TP5) (Sometimes, sir, I print simplified activity sheets. If time runs out, the students at least still have a quick task to do, TP5)

Depende rin po sa lesson, sir. Pero kadalasan, may nakahanda akong short drill o review question kapag nakita kong may oras pa o may part na di natapos (TP7) (It depends on the lesson, sir. But usually, I have a short drill or review question ready if I see that there is extra time or some parts were not finished, TP7)

Oo sir, lalo na pag may observation. Dapat ready ka sa lahat ng pwedeng mangyari, brownout, laptop issue, o kahit kabahan ka man (TP9) (Yes, sir, especially during observation. You must be ready for anything that could happen, brownouts, laptop issues, or even if you feel nervous, TP9)

Hindi po ako umaalis nang walang backup. Kahit simpleng writing activity lang, nilalagay ko sa folder ko para kung may short time, may magagawa pa rin ang mga bata (TP10) (I never leave without a backup. Even a simple writing activity is placed in my folder so that if there's little time, the students can still do something, TP10)

The responses indicate that teachers demonstrate flexibility and readiness by preparing quick drills, simplified tasks, and short alternative activities that can be deployed when time is limited or unexpected events occur. This strategy allows them to maintain lesson flow, manage student engagement, and respond effectively to classroom challenges. Teachers' ability to adapt quickly reflects resilience and ensures that learning objectives are met even under observation.

Classroom flexibility and readiness serve as essential coping strategies that complement contingency planning. Literature supports that teachers who can adjust lessons on the spot maintain instructional quality and student engagement. Bibon (2022) emphasizes that adaptability reduces teacher stress and allows for effective response to technical issues or time constraints. Granström et al. (2024) highlight that flexible planning increases teacher confidence and overall performance during observations. By preparing for both predictable and unpredictable scenarios, teachers exhibit professional competence, resilience, and the ability to ensure lesson continuity, which are critical during classroom observation and evaluation.

Table 7.4. Using Technology or Visual Aids Comfortable With

Emerging Themes	Code	Participant Responded
7.4.1 Teacher Comfort and Familiarity	Using familiar tools, sticking to what they know, minimizing stress	TP3, TP6, TP7, TP8, TP15
7.4.2 Blended Approach	Backup Using a mix of technology and manual materials, tested tech, alternative options	TP5, TP9, TP10, TP11, TP13

Legend: TP – Teachers' Participant

The table shows that teachers choose technology or visual aids based on their level of comfort and familiarity. Some teachers prefer tools they know well to reduce anxiety, while others adopt a blended

approach that combines technology with manual materials to ensure lesson continuity in case of technical issues.

The findings in Table 7.4 imply that teachers' comfort and familiarity with instructional technologies significantly contribute to smoother lesson delivery and reduced instructional stress during observations. Using tools, they are confident with enhances efficiency and minimizes technical disruptions; while adopting a blended or backup approach ensures continuity of instruction when technological issues arise. These results highlight the importance of strengthening teachers' technological proficiency and encouraging the preparation of alternative instructional materials to support reliable and effective teaching practices.

7.4.1 Teacher Comfort and Familiarity

The participants were asked how they select and use technology or visual aids during classroom observations. They responded and stated that:

Ako minsan sir kapag hindi ko alam gamitin or di pa ako sanay, hindi ko na muna ginagamit talaga (TP3) (Sometimes, sir, if I don't know how to use it or I am not yet familiar, I simply do not use it, TP3)

Ako sir, stick ako sa kung saan ako sanay. Kasi kapag pinilit mo sarili mo sa di mo kabisado, lalo ka lang kakabahan lalo na pag may observer (TP6) (I stick to what I'm familiar with, sir. Because if you force yourself to use something you don't know well, you will become more nervous, especially during observation, TP6)

Kung komportable ako sa PowerPoint, yun talaga ginagamit ko. Pero may mga time din na nag-multimedia ako kung gusto kong may impact, lalo na pag may mga bata na visual learners (TP7) (If I'm comfortable with PowerPoint, I use it. But sometimes I use multimedia if I want more impact, especially for visual learners, TP7)

Ako sir, medyo old-school pa rin. Mas gusto ko yung mga cutouts, charts, at flashcards. Parang mas authentic yung interaction (TP8) (I'm still a bit old-school, sir. I prefer cutouts, charts, and flashcards. The interaction feels more authentic, TP8)

Ako sir, basta komportable ako, yun ang ginagamit ko. Pwede technology, pwede manual, ang mahalaga, naituro ko nang maayos at naiintindihan ng mga bata (TP15) (As long as I'm comfortable, that's what I use, sir. It can be technology or manual. What matters is that I teach it well and the students understand, TP15)

Teachers prioritize comfort and familiarity in using technology or visual aids. When they are confident with the tools, they are less anxious and better able to focus on delivering the lesson. Some teachers combine technology with manual materials or ensure backups are ready to handle technical issues. This approach demonstrates that teacher self-efficacy and preparation are closely linked to instructional success and stress management during classroom observation.

Using technology or visual aids that teachers are comfortable with is both a practical and psychological coping strategy. Literature supports that teacher confidence in handling instructional tools enhances lesson delivery and classroom management (Marzano, 2024). Chiou (2023) notes that unfamiliar technology can increase anxiety and reduce teaching effectiveness, while having a mix of familiar and backup materials ensures lesson continuity. Granström et al. (2024) emphasize that adopting tools according

to teacher proficiency allows for better engagement of students, especially visual learners, and minimizes stress during observed lessons. Overall, teacher comfort with instructional tools improves professional composure, lesson effectiveness, and adaptability during classroom observations.

7.4.2 Blended or Backup Approach

The participants were asked how they use a combination of technology and manual materials or prepare alternative options during classroom observations. They stated that:

Depende rin sa topic, sir. Kung kailangan talaga ng visuals, gumagamit ako ng PowerPoint. Pero kung storytelling lang o discussion, whiteboard lang sapat na (TP5) (It also depends on the topic, sir. If visuals are really needed, I use PowerPoint. But if it's just storytelling or discussion, the whiteboard is enough, TP5)

Gumagamit ako ng technology pero siguradong tested na bago mag-demo. Ayoko nung biglang mag-hang o mawala ang sound habang nagrepresent (TP9) (I use technology but make sure it's tested before the demo. I don't like it freezing or losing sound while presenting, TP9)

Kahit may TV na sa classroom, sir, dala pa rin ako ng printed materials. Para kung magloko ang HDMI, tuloy pa rin ang lesson (TP10) (Even if there's a TV in the classroom, sir, I still bring printed materials. So, if the HDMI fails, the lesson can continue, TP10)

Gusto ko sir yung may halo, minsan PowerPoint, minsan chart. Para di nakakasawa sa bata at di rin ako ma-stress kung sakaling magka-technical issue (TP11) (I like having a mix, sir, sometimes PowerPoint, sometimes charts. So, it won't bore the students and I won't get stressed if there's a technical issue, TP11)

Para sa akin sir, okay gumagamit ng technology pero dapat may backup ka rin. Hindi pwedeng umasa lang sa kuryente (TP13) (For me, sir, it's okay to use technology but you must also have a backup. You cannot rely solely on electricity, TP13)

Teachers adopt a blended or backup approach to ensure lesson continuity and engagement. They combine technology with manual or traditional materials, test all devices beforehand, and prepare alternative options in case of technical failure. This approach reflects strategic planning and risk management, allowing teachers to deliver lessons effectively even under observation or unexpected technical challenges. The blended or backup approach highlights the importance of flexibility and preparedness in instructional delivery. Literature supports that combining technology with reliable traditional materials enhances student engagement and learning outcomes (Marzano, 2024). Chiou (2023) emphasizes that teachers who prepare alternatives reduce anxiety and avoid disruption in lesson flow. Granström et al. (2024) note that testing technology before class and having backup materials improves teacher confidence and maintains professional composure. By adopting a blended approach, teachers not only accommodate various learning preferences but also ensure smooth classroom management and uninterrupted instruction during observations.

Table 7.5. Staying Calm Through Breathing Exercises or Mindfulness

Emerging Themes	Code	Participant Responded
7.5.1 Mindfulness and Breathing Techniques	Deep breathing, inhale-exhale, meditation, prayer	TP1, TP2, TP3, TP6, TP11
7.5.2 Mental Preparation and Positive Self-Talk	Self-calming, visualization, thinking happy thoughts, affirmations	TP4, TP5, TP7, TP10, TP12

Legend: TP – Teachers' Participant

The table shows that teachers use mindfulness, breathing exercises, and mental preparation as strategies to manage stress and reduce anxiety during classroom observations. These techniques help them stay calm, maintain focus, and ensure confidence while teaching under observation. The results in Table 7.5 imply that mindfulness practices and mental preparation strategies help teachers manage stress and maintain composure during classroom observations. Techniques such as deep breathing, meditation, and prayer promote physiological calm, while positive self-talk, visualization, and affirmations enhance emotional resilience and confidence. These results highlight the importance of integrating stress-management training and mindfulness practices into teacher preparation programs to support effective, confident, and focused instructional delivery.

7.5.1 Mindfulness and Breathing Techniques

The participants were asked how they stay calm and manage anxiety during classroom observations. Their responses were:

Ganun nalang talaga ang gagawin, pakalmahin ang sarili, pero syempre sanay nadin tayo sa mga classroom observations medyo less na yung kaba (TP1) (You just have to calm yourself, but of course, we are already used to classroom observations so the anxiety is a bit less, TP1)

Yes, sir. Actually sir, lagi ko ginagawa bago magsimula. Hihinga muna ako ng malalim. Mag-inhale, exhale ako bago magsimula. Para ikalma yung aking sarili. Para hindi ako mawala sa flow ko. Sa flow ng aking lesson (TP2) (Yes, sir. I always do it before starting. I take deep breaths, inhale and exhale before starting to calm myself so I don't lose the flow of my lesson, TP2)

Ito talaga sir, bago mag-umpisa, inhale at exhale Malala talaga haha pampawala ba ng kaba (TP3) (This really works, sir. Before starting, I inhale and exhale. It really helps reduce anxiety, TP3)

Totoo sir, kapag kalmado ka sa simula, tuloy-tuloy na rin yung confidence mo hanggang matapos. Kaya lagi akong nag-i-inhale-exhale sa gilid habang naghihintay (TP6) (That's true, sir. If you're calm at the start, your confidence continues until the end. That's why I always do inhale-exhale on the side while waiting, TP6)

Ginagawa ko yan sir bago ako pumasok sa classroom. Inhale-exhale tapos smile. Nakakatulong talaga para hindi ka magmukhang tense sa mga bata (TP11) (I do that before entering the classroom, sir. Inhale-exhale then smile. It really helps so you don't appear tense to the students, TP11)

The responses indicate that teachers actively use breathing exercises and mindfulness techniques to manage anxiety and stress during classroom observations. In addition, some employ prayer, visualization, or positive self-talk to boost emotional readiness. These strategies help teachers maintain composure, focus on lesson delivery, and project confidence, demonstrating that emotional readiness is closely linked to effective teaching under observation.

Emotional readiness and stress management are critical for teachers facing classroom observations. Literature suggests that mindfulness and breathing exercises reduce physiological and psychological stress (Milenković, 2024). Myers (2012) notes that self-calming techniques enhance concentration and maintain instructional flow even under evaluative conditions. Moreover, positive self-talk and visualization reinforce teacher confidence, aligning with Chiou (2023), who emphasizes that mental preparation supports professional performance. Combining technical preparation (lesson plans, materials) with emotional coping strategies (mindfulness, breathing, affirmations) allows teachers to manage stress effectively, ensuring smoother lesson delivery and higher teaching efficacy during observations.

7.5.2 Mental Preparation and Positive Self-Talk

The participants were asked how they mentally prepare and use self-talk strategies to manage anxiety during classroom observations. They responded and stated that:

Minsan sir, bago ako pumasok sa room, tahimik muna ako sa isang tabi. Iniisip ko lang na normal day lang, parang regular teaching lang para hindi ako tense (TP4) (Sometimes, sir, before entering the room, I stay quiet in a corner. I just think it's a normal day, like regular teaching, so I don't get tense, TP4)

Ako sir, nagpe-pray muna. Kasama na rin sa mindfulness ko yun. Pagkatapos, deep breathing tapos smile lang. Nakakatulong talaga (TP5) (I pray first, sir. That is also part of my mindfulness. After that, I do deep breathe and just smile. It really helps, TP5)

Hindi ako masyadong marunong sa mindfulness pero ginagawa ko lang, sir, mag-isip ng happy thoughts bago mag-start. Para hindi kabado (TP7) (I'm not very skilled in mindfulness, but I just think of happy thoughts before starting, sir. So I don't get nervous, TP7)

Kapag sobrang kaba sir, sinasabi ko lang sa sarili ko na, "Kaya mo yan." Tapos hinga lang nang malalim. Parang mental reset lang (TP10) (When I'm very nervous, sir, I just tell myself "You can do this." Then I take a deep breath. It's like a mental reset, TP10)

Ako sir, kapag sobra ang kaba, pinipikit ko lang saglit ang mata ko, tapos nagco-concentrate sa breathing. After nun, okay na ulit (TP12) (When I'm too nervous, sir, I just close my eyes for a moment, then focus on breathing. After that, I'm okay again, TP12)

The responses indicate that teachers use mental preparation and positive self-talk as key strategies to manage anxiety and stress during classroom observations. Techniques such as visualizing a normal teaching day, thinking happy thoughts, praying, and affirming personal capability help teachers regulate their emotions before and during the lesson. These strategies promote emotional stability, confidence, and focus, allowing teachers to deliver lessons smoothly and interact effectively with students even under the pressure of being observed.

Mental preparation and positive self-talk are critical for emotional readiness. Literature supports that cognitive strategies like self-talk, visualization, and affirmations reduce anxiety and improve task performance (Milenković, 2024; Myers, 2012). Chiou (2023) emphasizes that teachers who use mental coping mechanisms are better able to maintain professional composure and instructional flow during evaluations. Moreover, combining these psychological strategies with mindfulness or breathing exercises enhances overall stress management and lesson effectiveness (Granström et al., 2024). This demonstrates that preparing mentally and using positive self-talk are essential psychological strategies that complement technical lesson preparation, allowing teachers to maintain confidence and resilience during classroom observations.

Table 7.6. Adjusting Language Use to Balance Formality and Clarity

Emerging Themes	Code	Participant Responded
7.6.1 Language Adaptation for Student Understanding	Simplifying terms, translation, using familiar words, code-switching	TP1, TP2, TP3, TP5, TP7
7.6.2 Balancing Formality and Clarity	Formal language, contextual examples, professionalism while being understandable	TP6, TP8, TP10, TP11, TP15

Legend: TP – Teachers’ Participant

The table shows that teachers strategically adjust their language during classroom observations to ensure students understand the lesson. They simplify complex terms, switch between languages, and balance formal speech with clear explanations, ensuring lessons are comprehensible without sacrificing professionalism.

It implies that teachers’ strategic language use is key to ensuring both clarity and professionalism in instruction. Adapting language through simplification, translation, or code-switching helps students understand content, while balancing formality with contextual examples maintains instructional credibility and effectiveness. These results highlight the importance of developing teachers’ communication skills to enhance learner comprehension, engagement, and confidence in delivering lessons under evaluative conditions.

7.6.1 Language Adaptation for Student Understanding

The participants were asked how they adjust their language during classroom observations to ensure students understand the lesson. Their responses were:

Magkakaroon ng sandwich technique, mas isalin mo sa mga mas naiintindihan ng mga bata (TP1) (There’s a sandwich technique, you translate it into words that the children can understand better, TP1)

Ikaw talagang mag-adjust kasi kung ang bata hindi makaunawa, hindi mo naman maaasahan na sila ang makakapag-adjust para sa iyo lalo na mga elementary kasi yan. So kailangan talaga, ikaw talaga ready ka na mag-adjust (TP2) (You really have to adjust because if the child cannot understand, you cannot expect them to adjust for you, especially in elementary. So, you must be ready to adjust, TP2)

Yes, ako sir talaga nag-aadjust depende sa bata, kapag hindi nila gets edi I translate kesa naman hindi talaga nila maintindihan ang lesson

(TP3) (Yes sir, I really adjust depending on the child. If they don’t get it, I translate it so they can understand the lesson, TP3)

Ako sir, gumagamit talaga ako ng Taglish. Halimbawa English yung subject pero kapag blanko na yung mga bata, nagta-Tagalog na ako. Basta malinaw, okay na yun (TP5) (I really use Taglish, sir. For example, if the subject is English but the children blank out, I switch to Tagalog. As long as it's clear, it's okay, TP5)

Tinitingnan ko kung naiintindihan nila yung word. Pag hindi, agad kong pinapaliwanag in simpler words. Para tuloy-tuloy lang ang lesson, walang natatambakan (TP7) (I check if they understand the word. If not, I immediately explain in simpler words. So, the lesson continues smoothly, nothing gets piled up, TP7)

The responses show that teachers actively adjust their language use to match students' comprehension levels. They employ techniques such as simplifying terms, translating, code-switching between English and Filipino, and giving contextual examples to maintain clarity. Teachers recognize that formal language alone may not guarantee understanding, so balancing formality with accessibility is essential to ensure effective lesson delivery.

Language adaptation during classroom observations demonstrates the importance of cognitive and communicative flexibility. Archer et al. (2016) highlight that teachers who adjust their language to students' needs enhance engagement and comprehension. Granström et al. (2024) note that balancing formal instruction with clear explanations helps reduce student confusion and fosters an inclusive learning environment. Moreover, Chiou (2023) emphasizes that the ability to switch between languages or simplify concepts reflects teacher responsiveness and professional competence. By tailoring their language, teachers ensure that classroom observations accurately reflect both their instructional skill and their ability to facilitate meaningful student learning.

7.6.2 Balancing Formality with Clarity

The participants were asked how they maintain professional and formal language while ensuring that students can still understand the lesson during classroom observations. They stated that:

Kapag observation sir, gusto mo rin ipakita na formal at maayos ka magsalita. Pero syempre kung hindi nakakasabay yung bata, kailangan mo talagang mag-adjust. Hindi pwedeng puro "pa-impress" (TP6) (During observation, sir, you also want to show that you speak formally and properly. But of course, if the children cannot keep up, you really need to adjust. You can't just "impress," TP6)

Ako sir, kapag napansin kong parang tulala na yung mga bata, sinasalin ko agad sa Filipino. Mas okay na naiintindihan nila kesa puro English na walang sumasagot

(TP8) (Sir, when I notice the children are zoning out, I immediately switch to Filipino. It's better that they understand than using only English with no response, TP8)

Ang ginagawa ko sir, kahit English lesson, tinatry kong i-explain in context. Para habang natututo sila ng English, naiintindihan din nila yung meaning sa sarili nilang language (TP10) (What I do, sir, even for an English lesson, I try to explain it in context. So, while they are learning English, they also understand the meaning in their own language, TP10)

Ang importante sa akin sir, naiintindihan ng bata yung tinuturo ko. Hindi naman ito contest kung sino ang pinakaformal magsalita. Basta clear, okay na (TP11) (The important thing for me, sir, is that the child understands what I'm teaching. This isn't a contest on who speaks most formally. As long as it's clear, it's fine, TP11)

Kahit may observer's sir, hindi ako nag-o-overdo sa formal terms. Kasi ang tunay na teaching, yung naiintindihan ng bata, hindi lang yung magaling pakinggan (TP15) (Even with observers, sir, I don't overdo formal terms. True teaching is what the child understands, not just what sounds impressive, TP15)

The responses show that teachers balance formality and clarity by using professional language while remaining sensitive to students' comprehension. They adapt by giving contextual explanations, switching to the students' language when necessary, and moderating formal terms. This strategy ensures lessons are both professional and accessible, maintaining the integrity of the observation while prioritizing learning.

Balancing formality with clarity reflects a teacher's pedagogical adaptability and communicative competence. Literature emphasizes that effective teachers adjust their language to student needs while upholding professional standards (Archer et al., 2016; Milenković, 2024). Chiou (2023) notes that teachers who prioritize clarity over rigid formality enhance student engagement and understanding during observed lessons. Moreover, Granström et al. (2024) highlight that blending formal and familiar language fosters an inclusive learning environment, ensuring that classroom observations accurately reflect both teaching skill and responsiveness to learners. By integrating clarity, professionalism, and adaptability, teachers create an environment conducive to learning while demonstrating effective instructional practice under observation.

The findings of the study reveal that teachers employ a variety of coping mechanisms to manage the challenges they face during classroom observations, reflecting their adaptability, resilience, and commitment to maintaining instructional quality. One of the most prominent strategies is advance preparation. Teachers emphasized the importance of preparing lesson plans ahead of time, consulting with master teachers, revising lessons repeatedly, and ensuring that all instructional materials are ready before the observation. Such preparation not only allows lessons to run smoothly but also helps teachers manage the stress associated with being observed. Participants reported that having lessons ready well in advance reduces last-minute panic and builds confidence, enabling them to focus on teaching rather than worrying about gaps or errors. This finding is consistent with previous studies, which suggest that well-prepared teachers demonstrate greater classroom control and are better able to respond flexibly to unexpected situations (Zaare, 2012; Archer et al., 2016).

Teachers also highlighted the importance of organizing the classroom environment to minimize distractions. They described arranging seating, ensuring classrooms are clean, and strategically placing materials to create a conducive learning atmosphere. Attention to visual appeal, noise control, and overall orderliness not only supports student engagement but also reflects professionalism during observations. By controlling their environment, teachers manage both practical challenges and the psychological pressures of being evaluated, which aligns with studies indicating that a well-structured classroom enhances teaching efficiency and student focus (Zaare, 2012; Archer et al., 2016).

Flexibility and contingency planning emerged as another key strategy. Teachers reported preparing backup activities, simplified exercises, or drills to handle unexpected interruptions, technical issues, or time constraints. Having alternative plans allowed them to maintain lesson continuity and keep students engaged, even when circumstances changed suddenly. This proactive approach helps reduce anxiety, enabling teachers to adapt seamlessly without compromising learning outcomes, consistent with research that

highlights the benefits of adaptability in instructional effectiveness (Bhebhe & Nxumalo, 2015; Granström et al., 2024).

The careful selection of instructional materials and technology also featured prominently among coping strategies. Many teachers relied on tools they were familiar with, such as PowerPoint presentations, charts, and flashcards, while also preparing backups to prevent disruptions. This approach reflects both competence and confidence, ensuring that teaching remains effective even when unexpected challenges arise. Studies indicate that teachers' comfort with instructional tools directly influences engagement, lesson quality, and stress reduction during observations (Chiou, 2023; Marzano, 2024).

Emotional coping strategies were equally significant. Teachers frequently used mindfulness, deep breathing, positive self-talk, visualization, and prayer to manage anxiety and remain composed during observations. These techniques enabled them to maintain professional demeanor, focus on instruction, and deliver lessons effectively under evaluative pressure. Such emotional regulation supports teacher performance and reduces stress in observation settings (Marzaini et al., 2024; Granström et al., 2024).

Adjusting language for clarity and professionalism was another tactic. Teachers reported modifying their language by simplifying terms, using code-switching, or contextualizing explanations to ensure student understanding while maintaining a professional tone. This demonstrates both cognitive flexibility and attentiveness to students' needs, enhancing engagement and learning. Research suggests that such linguistic adjustments reflect professional competence and help ensure that classroom observations accurately capture instructional quality without compromising student comprehension (Archer et al., 2016; Granström et al., 2024).

Collaboration and reflection were also integral to teachers' coping mechanisms. Reviewing past feedback, discussing strategies with colleagues, and reflecting on previous experiences allowed teachers to improve their teaching methods, build confidence, and reduce the stress associated with classroom observations. Peer support and reflective practices foster professional growth and resilience, helping teachers approach evaluations as opportunities for development rather than threats (Reños & Pontillas, 2024; Thom, 2020).

Teachers' coping mechanisms during classroom observations involve a careful combination of preparation, adaptability, emotional regulation, and reflection. These strategies not only alleviate anxiety but also enhance instructional effectiveness, illustrating that classroom observation can serve as a catalyst for professional growth. Teachers' proactive, flexible, and reflective approaches highlight their resilience and dedication to providing quality education even under evaluative conditions.

Significant relationship between the common teaching practices and challenges encountered by teachers' respondents during the conduct of classroom observation

The results reveal no significant relationship between the two variables, indicating that the frequency or consistency of teachers' best teaching practices does not necessarily influence the extent of challenges they experience during observations. This suggests that even teachers who regularly demonstrate effective instructional strategies, classroom management, and assessment practices may still face difficulties when being observed, likely due to situational pressures such as time constraints, performance anxiety, and the presence of evaluators. The finding underscores that challenges during classroom observation are not solely determined by teaching competence but may also stem from contextual and psychological factors inherent to the observation process.

The finding that there is no significant relationship between teachers' best teaching practices and the challenges they encounter during classroom observations highlights a complex reality in the teaching profession. It indicates that the difficulties teachers experience during observations are not always reflective of their teaching competence but are often influenced by contextual, environmental, and psychological factors. According to Kim and Kim (2020), even highly skilled teachers tend to modify or rehearse their instructional approaches during observed sessions due to heightened awareness of being evaluated. This

“performance pressure” can lead to temporary disruptions in their natural teaching flow, regardless of their usual level of expertise.

Similarly, Labad et al. (2024) noted that classroom observations often create artificial teaching conditions, where teachers’ focus shifts from authentic instruction to compliance with rubric-based criteria. This situation may cause stress and anxiety, even among those who consistently exhibit effective teaching practices. Marzano (2024) emphasized that the presence of evaluators and the formal nature of observation procedures can trigger self-consciousness and fear of negative feedback, which interfere with teachers’ confidence and spontaneity during instruction.

Emotional and psychological factors play a critical role in shaping teachers’ experiences during observations. Bhebhe and Nxumalo (2015) found that observation-related anxiety affects both novice and experienced teachers, suggesting that expertise does not necessarily shield educators from stress. Likewise, Fayo and Hilario (2023) revealed that teachers often feel pressured to “perform” rather than teach authentically when observed, highlighting how external expectations can override pedagogical competence. These findings align with the concept of the Hawthorne Effect, where individuals alter their behavior simply because they know they are being observed (Sugot & Ladia, 2024).

Environmental conditions also contribute to these challenges. Thom (2020) and Chiou (2023) both observed that logistical factors such as limited preparation time, large class sizes, and technological issues can affect teachers’ performance during observed lessons, regardless of their instructional skill. This indicates that situational constraints, rather than lack of competence, often explain why even effective teachers experience stress or difficulty during classroom observations.

It supports the idea that teaching expertise does not eliminate the challenges associated with being observed. Instead, these difficulties stem from a combination of psychological pressures, contextual constraints, and structural aspects of the observation process, reaffirming the importance of conducting observations within a supportive, non-threatening, and developmental framework (Granström et al., 2024; Torres et al., 2024).

Table 8. Pearson Correlation for the Hypothesis 1

	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i> -value	Description
Occurrence of Teaching Practices × Number of Challenges	0.03	0.616	No significant relationship

Significant relationship between the challenges encountered by teachers’ respondents and the coping mechanism they employ during the conduct of classroom observation?

The results indicate no significant relationship between the two variables, suggesting that the number or intensity of challenges faced by teachers does not directly correspond to the number or type of coping strategies they use. This implies that coping behaviors may be influenced more by individual dispositions, prior experiences, or professional attitudes rather than by the specific challenges encountered. In other words, even teachers who experience fewer difficulties may still engage in proactive coping strategies, while those facing more challenges may not necessarily employ additional or varied mechanisms. The finding shows the complex and individualized nature of coping, suggesting that teachers’ responses to observation-related stress are shaped by personal resilience, self-efficacy, and familiarity with the observation process rather than by the mere frequency of challenges faced.

The finding that there is no significant relationship between the challenges teachers face and the coping mechanisms they employ during classroom observation reflects the complex and highly individualized nature of teacher coping. Research suggests that coping behaviors are not merely reactive to stressors but are shaped by personal traits, professional experiences, and teachers’ perceptions of control and efficacy. According to Lazarus and Folkman’s (1984) Transactional Model of Stress and Coping,

individuals respond to stress based on their appraisal of the situation and their perceived ability to manage it. This means that two teachers facing similar challenges may adopt entirely different coping strategies depending on their mindset, confidence, and emotional regulation.

In the context of teaching, self-efficacy and resilience play a crucial role in determining how educators respond to stressful situations. Bandura (1997) explained that teachers with higher self-efficacy are more likely to engage in proactive coping behaviors, such as advance lesson planning and reflective practice, regardless of the intensity of challenges they face. Similarly, Mogotsi and Dlamini (2022) found that teachers who possess strong emotional resilience tend to rely on stable coping mechanisms—such as mindfulness, collaboration, and self-reflection—rather than adjusting their responses based solely on external difficulties.

Studies in the Philippine setting support this perspective. Reños and Pontillas (2024) revealed that Filipino teachers’ coping responses during classroom observations are often shaped by habitual professional practices and internal motivation rather than the situational challenges themselves. Their study emphasized that teachers’ coping tendencies are built over time through experience, collegial support, and repeated exposure to evaluative contexts. In a related study, Bibon (2022) argued that coping strategies such as emotional regulation, collaboration with peers, and reflective practice are sustained behaviors that teachers employ as part of their professional identity, not just as temporary reactions to stress.

Furthermore, Myers (2012) highlighted that the variability in coping responses among teachers reflects individual differences in personality, emotional stability, and work orientation. Teachers who are naturally organized and reflective may employ coping strategies such as planning ahead or seeking feedback even in low-stress situations. Conversely, those with limited coping awareness may struggle to apply effective mechanisms despite facing greater challenges. This aligns with Granström et al. (2024), who emphasized that the effectiveness of coping depends more on personal adaptability and emotional intelligence than on the external magnitude of stressors.

Overall, the absence of a significant relationship between challenges and coping mechanisms underscores that coping is not always proportional to the stress experienced. Instead, it is influenced by deeper psychological factors such as self-efficacy, resilience, emotional stability, and professional identity. This highlights the need for professional development programs that not only address situational challenges but also build teachers’ long-term emotional strength, reflective capacity, and adaptive coping skills.

Table 9. Pearson Correlation for the Hypothesis 2

	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i> -value	Description
Number of Challenges × Number of Coping Mechanism	0.01	0.890	No significant relationship

Summary of Findings

This study investigated the conformity of classroom observation with teaching practices among selected elementary schools in the Division of Puerto Princesa City, District II. The results provided important insights into how teachers’ daily practices align with the standards and expectations set during classroom observations, as well as the factors influencing this conformity.

In terms of the demographic profile, the majority of the respondents were classroom teachers, 175 teachers or 80%, with master teachers comprising 45 teachers or 20%. Most have been teaching for six to fifteen years, 111 teachers or 50%, while 81 teachers or 37% have one to five years of experience, and 28 teachers or 13% have 16 to 27 years of experience, suggesting that the respondents are generally in the early to mid stages of their teaching careers. The majority handled Grade 5, 63 teachers or 29%, and Grade 6, 41 teachers or 19%, learners, with many teaching multiple learning areas such as Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao, 154 teachers or 70%, Mathematics, 91 teachers or 41%, and Araling Panlipunan, 76 teachers

or 35%. Regarding educational attainment, most respondents held a bachelor's degree, 148 teachers or 67%, while 58 teachers or 26% had earned units in a master's program, and 14 teachers or 6% had completed a master's degree, reflecting continuous efforts for professional growth and advancement.

The school profile revealed that most respondents came from large schools, 145 teachers or 66%, indicating diverse teaching environments and larger student populations. The teachers-to-master teacher ratio was commonly 10:1, 73 teachers or 33%, implying that while mentorship exists, it may not be frequent enough to ensure close instructional supervision. Other ratios included 5:1, 49 teachers or 22%, 14:1, 42 teachers or 19%, 7:1, 18 teachers or 8%, 22:1, 18 teachers or 8%, 15:1, 15 teachers or 3%, 3:1, 1 teacher or 1%, and no master teacher, 7 teachers or 5%. Most schools had functional classrooms, 220 teachers or 100%, and sufficient teaching facilities such as LCD projectors, 220 teachers or 100%, internet access, 211 teachers or 96%, libraries, 206 teachers or 94%, and learning modules or textbooks, 210 teachers or 95%. Some lacked specialized rooms like laboratories, 0 teachers or 0%, and audio-visual equipment was limited, 41 teachers or 19%, suggesting unequal access to modern instructional resources.

Findings on the occurrence of best teaching practices showed a strong pattern of excellence among teachers, with an overall mean of 4.52, interpreted as always. Among the five domains, classroom management, mean 4.98, ranked the highest, indicating consistent adherence to effective discipline and positive classroom environments. Teaching strategies, mean 4.59, and instructional materials, mean 4.58, also received always ratings, reflecting the frequent use of varied strategies and well-prepared materials aligned with curriculum standards. On the other hand, time management, mean 4.04, and assessment and evaluation, mean 4.40, were described as often, suggesting that these areas are regularly practiced but may need further consistency to meet full conformity with observation expectations.

The analysis of teachers' daily teaching practices supported these findings. High mean ratings were observed in domains such as classroom management, where teachers always maintained order, respect, and positive reinforcement, mean 4.94–5.00. Similarly, teachers consistently demonstrated the use of diverse instructional strategies and effective use of materials. However, slightly lower means in time management, mean 4.01–4.09, and assessment and evaluation, mean 3.99–4.96, indicate areas where conformity with observed standards could be improved, specifically in pacing lessons, optimizing instructional time, and aligning assessments with learning objectives.

The findings also revealed that while teachers always exhibit best practices in most domains, their actual teaching practices sometimes only often conform to what is expected during classroom observation. This partial conformity may be influenced by contextual challenges such as limited time, resource constraints, and observation-related pressure. Teachers reported difficulties in preparing materials, adjusting lesson pacing, and managing anxiety during observed sessions, which could momentarily affect their usual performance. Nonetheless, they addressed these through proactive coping strategies such as early lesson preparation, classroom organization, and self-regulation techniques.

Correlation analyses revealed no significant relationship between best teaching practices and challenges encountered during classroom observation, $r = 0.03$, $p = 0.616$, and between challenges and coping mechanisms, $r = 0.01$, $p = 0.890$. This implies that the conformity between classroom observation and actual teaching practices does not merely depend on the challenges teachers face, but rather on their consistent commitment to quality instruction, regardless of external pressures.

Overall, the study found that teachers in the Division of Puerto Princesa City exhibit high levels of conformity between classroom observation and actual teaching practices, particularly in classroom management, instructional preparation, and teaching strategies. However, areas such as time management and assessment alignment show moderate conformity, suggesting the need for more focused professional support and developmental feedback during post-observation conferences to further enhance the alignment between observation standards and authentic teaching behavior.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that classroom observations generally mirror teachers' real teaching practices. Most teachers remain consistent with their usual routines, suggesting that what is seen during observations is an authentic reflection of their daily work in the classroom. However, certain external factors, such as time pressure and feelings of anxiety, still influence their performance. Even well-prepared teachers may experience stress that slightly alters their natural teaching flow. Despite these challenges, many teachers are able to maintain consistency by using effective coping strategies such as, preparing lessons ahead of time, staying organized, and drawing moral support from their colleagues and school leaders. Above all, the study highlights the importance of fostering a supportive observation culture. When classroom observations are conducted with fairness, empathy, and constructive feedback, teachers become more confident, motivated, and open to continuous professional growth.

Recommendations

This study presents several recommendations to make classroom observation a more meaningful and developmental process for everyone involved in the teaching and learning community.

1. The Department of Education is encouraged to strengthen the implementation and monitoring of classroom observation by conducting annual division-wide seminars and calibration workshops for school heads and observers focusing on the proper use of observation tools, inter-rater reliability, and ethical observation practices. These activities may include video-based lesson analyses and scoring alignment exercises to ensure fairness and consistency. The establishment of a division monitoring team to conduct periodic validation observations and the development of online refresher and certification courses for observers are also recommended. In addition, DepEd should institutionalize peer observation and mentoring programs across schools with clear guidelines, timelines, and documentation to promote collaborative professional learning.

2. School Heads and Master Teachers are encouraged to create a supportive and non-threatening observation culture by organizing school-based INSET sessions and quarterly mentoring workshops that focus on effective classroom observation, coaching, and feedback-giving skills. They should implement regular peer observation cycles and conduct monthly Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions to address common instructional challenges identified during observations. Timely, specific, and constructive feedback should be provided within three to five working days, accompanied by individualized professional growth plans to ensure that classroom observations lead to meaningful instructional improvement.

3. Teachers are encouraged to view classroom observation as a professional growth opportunity by actively participating in pre- and post-observation conferences, peer mentoring activities, and collaborative lesson planning sessions. Attendance in school-based or division-level seminars on reflective teaching and self-assessment using PPST indicators is recommended to strengthen instructional competence. Teachers may also maintain reflection journals or professional portfolios to document feedback received, action steps taken, and improvements in teaching practices, thereby promoting continuous professional development.

4. Learners should be oriented through classroom or school-level briefings on the purpose of classroom observation to help them understand its role in improving teaching and learning. Their active participation during observed lessons and their honest responses through structured feedback tools such as learner perception surveys, exit slips, or reflection forms are essential in providing an authentic picture of classroom dynamics. Encouraging learner engagement and cooperation during observations will contribute to more accurate and meaningful evaluation of instructional practices.

5. The researcher is encouraged to extend the findings of this study by conducting longitudinal and comparative research that examines the relationship between classroom observation practices and actual

teaching performance across different schools or divisions. Collaboration with educators and administrators may lead to more comprehensive insights, while the development of training modules, seminar-workshop materials, or coaching guides based on the study's results may support INSETs, LAC sessions, and other professional development initiatives aimed at improving instructional quality and educational leadership.

6. Future researchers are encouraged to replicate this study in secondary schools or other educational divisions to broaden understanding of classroom observation practices. Further research may also examine the long-term effects of observation feedback, mentoring, and coaching programs on teachers' professional growth, instructional effectiveness, and student learning outcomes. Exploring specific interventions such as peer coaching, video-based observation, or digital observation tools will help establish classroom observation as a transformative strategy for improving teaching and learning.

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